

The Grammar of the Kōxō Language

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1. Introduction

Kōxō is a constructed language designed with the primary goal of being logical and having minimal ambiguity. It achieves this goal primarily by declining determiners for specificity and distributivity - features that are very rare in natural languages and only appear in a rudimentary form even when they are present.

Apart from this, there are several other minor innovations, such as its case system; a larger set of pronouns; a well developed aspectual system which includes two imperfect aspects and a distinction between the plain and habitual aspect (in particular, a distinction between them in the present tense); a distinction between restrictive and non-restrictive relative clauses; a separate form for conjunctive adverbs; different translations for different meanings of the words 'how' and 'why' (the explanatives); the 'coda form' of verbs, adjectives, adverbs, and determiners; a null tense for verbs; a complex nominalisation system; the identifier and explanative prefix constructions; an epistemic vs deontic distinction in some verbs; and the inclusion of Booleans.

Within the restrictions of this primary goal, it is also intended to be simple and easy to learn. It achieves this through a regular grammar, linguistic purity (in the sense that no word contains roots that are outside the language, not in the sense that none of the language's roots are derived from words outside the language), and the avoidance of unnecessary and superfluous features that do not contribute to achieving the primary goal.

It could be argued that the language's phonology should be simpler, however it was necessary to balance the simplicity of the phonology with other requirements. In particular, the inclusion of initial consonant mutations and use of *rendaku* in word derivation would not have been possible without sacrificing some phonological simplicity.

A note on gloss: To make this work accessible to non-linguists, and due to a desire to present the kōxō text without modification, there are some differences between the glossing used in this book and conventional Leipzig glossing. Firstly, the kōxō text is given without hyphens, so it can be seen in its true, unmodified form. Secondly, the glossing contains a mixture of Leipzig glossing abbreviations, English text, and kōxō text, since some of the kōxō is either completely innovative and cannot be expressed using existing glossing abbreviations or too complex to express succinctly with glossing abbreviations.

2. Phonology and orthography

2.1 Consonants

	Labial	Dental	Alveolar	Velar	Glottal
Plosive	p b		t d	k g	
Fricative	f v	θ~ð	s~z		h
Affricate					
Nasal	m		n		
Rhotic			r		
Approximant			l	w	

2.2 Vowels and diphthongs

	Front		Central		Back	
	tense	lax	tense	lax	tense	lax
Close	i:	ɪ			u:	ʊ
Mid	e:	ɛ			o:	ɔ
Open			a:	æ		

The 'macronised vowels' are written with a macron. For example, [e:] is written ē, [ɛ] is written e. The exception is [i:], which is written i, with [ɪ] written as ɪ.

The plain vowels o and e (pronounced [ɔ] and [ɛ]) can be used at the end of words but must be lengthened in most cases, articles being an exception. This is indicated with a circumflex accent. For example, there are the words dô [dɔ:] and dê [dɛ:]. These long vowels can only be used at the end of a word, except in compound words where they can appear at the end of a word forming part of the compound word.

Diphthongs are [ai], [oi], and [au].

2.3 The alphabet

The following table shows the kōxō alphabet in kōxō alphabetical order:

Letter	Phoneme	Name of letter
a	a	a:
ā	a:	a: makro:
e	ɛ	e:
ē	e:	e: makro:

l	l	i:
i	i:	i: makro:
o	o	o:
ō	o:	o: makro:
u	u	u:
ū	u:	u: makro:
p	p	pe:
b	b	bi:
t	t	te:
d	d	di:
k	k	ke:
g	g	gi:
f	f	fa:
v	v	vi:
m	m	me:
n	n	no:
x	ŋ	ŋo:
z	θ/ ð	θa:
s	s/ z	se:
z	z	za:
w	w	wa:
h	h	ha:
l	l	le:
r	r	ro:

Note that kōxō does not use capital letters, which is why none of the kōxō text in this document contains capital letters, even at the beginning of a sentence.

2.4 Initial mutations

Kōxō has a system of initial mutations whereby the initial letter of a word is mutated to convey grammatical information. The initial mutations are shown in the table below:

	Mutation
p	b
t	d
k	g
f	v
l	r
n	x
m	w

s	z
vowel	h

These mutations are used to put words in the nominative case. They are also used to form new words in that the second component of compound words is mutated.

2.5 Phonotactics

A kōxō word may only begin in a vowel or single unmutated consonant i.e. p, t, k, f, l, n, m, or s.

A noun may end in any of the unmutated consonants as well as a voiced plosive (b, d, g) or v. The main syllable structures for a root noun, adjective, or adverb in kōxō are CVC and CVCeC. In the latter case, the 'e' functions as an unstressed vowel i.e. a schwa. The CVCeC form is sometimes reduced to CVCC in nouns, as will be explained in [section 5](#). Verbal roots mainly have either a syllable structure of CVC or CVCC, ignoring suffixes and prefixes.

The vowel of a monosyllabic noun ending in s, n, or l must be long. Hence we have tās, tēs, tis, tōs, and tūs but not tas, tes, tis, tos or tus. The vowel of a monosyllabic noun ending in a consonant cluster must be short. Hence we may have task, tesk, tisk, tosk, and tusk but not tāsk, tēsk, tisk, tōsk, or tūsk.

3. Word order and parts of speech

kōxō is verb-initial, with the predominant word order being VSO. VOS can be used if convenient i.e. if the subject of the verb is long. For example

paro sen ze wan i fono sē
do.PST it NOM.se NOM.man NOM.o live.PST there
the man that lived there did it

A list of parts of speech in kōxō is given below. Many of these parts of speech have their own chapter in this document.

nouns

 pronouns

markers

determiners

predeterminers

verbs

 auxiliary verbs

adverbs

 first-order

 second-order

 pre-auxiliary

 conjunctive

sō and kō

4. Case

4.1 Nominative and plain case

Kōxō is a marked nominative language. Hence accusative noun phrases are identical to noun phrases coming after prepositions.

The nominative is formed by mutating the initial consonant. Not only nouns but also determiners, verbs, adjectives, and adverbs can all be put into the nominative case.

In a nominative noun phrase, the first consonant of the noun, determiner, and any adjectives and adverbs are mutated. Hence, essentially every word in the noun phrase is mutated, with exceptions for words such as 'and' or 'or'.

Examples:

fiso ze dē gome wan se tav
see.PST NOM.se NOM.very NOM.big NOM.man se tree
The very big man saw the tree

kino ze dē gome wan
go.PST NOM.se NOM.very NOM.big NOM.man
The very big man went

Verb phrases in kōxō may also be declined for case. In a nominative verb phrase, the first consonants of the verb and any adverbs are mutated. For example:

mi dō rende ginē kek
be.PRS NOM.too NOM.slow-COD NOM.go.INF bad
going too slowly is bad

The arguments of the verb are not mutated (except for the nominative argument of the verb, which is in the nominative separately from the verb being in the nominative). For example:

mi barē ga sen kek
be.PRS NOM.do.INF NOM.he it bad
him doing it is bad

4.2 A note on terminology

Throughout this document, we will refer to anything that is marked as the 'argument' of its marker, and anything that is linked to a verb by case as an 'argument' of the verb.

Some linguists like to refer to things marked as 'objects' of the marker. For example, they might refer to the 'object of a preposition'. We avoid this terminology in order to avoid confusion with the object of a verb, reserving the term 'object' exclusively for that which is in the accusative case. Hence, the subject and object are both arguments of the verb, but the subject is not an object of the verb.

5. Nouns

Nouns are declined for case, number, and state. The cases have already been discussed. They are nominative and plain. In addition, there are two states - the construct and plain. The construct is used when a noun is followed by a relative clause. For example:

se molk o pivo xa
se milk.CNS o drink.PST NOM.I

se tosm i fiso xa
se star.CNS NOM.o see.PST NOM.I
the star that I saw

Note that the syllable boundaries in the last example are *tos | mi | fi | so | xa*.

It is also used in genitive constructions **and when suffixes are added to the word**. For example:

kals ev molek
glass.CNS of milk
glass of milk

The plain state is used elsewhere i.e. when a noun appears alone or with an adjectival phrase or prepositional phrase. For example:

pivo xa se molek
drink.PST NOM.I se milk
I drank the milk

pivo xa se talde molek
drink.PST NOM.I se white.COD milk
I drank the white milk

mo ze wolek en se fridge
be.PST NOM.se NOM.milk in se fridge

se molek en se fridge
se milk in se fridge

The construct and plain states are only distinct in words with the CVCVC syllable structure. In shorter words, such as *man*, they are the same.

An example of noun declension is shown below:

	singular		plural
	plain	construct	
plain	molek	molk	molken
nominative	wolek	wolk	wolken

Nouns must be accompanied by a determiner, except for indefinite uncountable nouns and proper nouns. Plural nouns are always accompanied by a determiner.

6. Pronouns

6.1 Basic pronouns

	plain	nom.	dat.
I	na	xa	nem
you	fu	vu	fem
he/ she	ka	ga	kem
it	sen	zen	sem
we (inc)	mas	was	mesem
we (exc)	men	wen	menem
you (pl)	fo	vo	fam
they	kê	gê	kam
they (inanimate)	sê	zê	sam

Notes:

There is no gender in pronouns. There is no distinction between 'he' and 'she'.

The dative case exists only in pronouns.

sê means 'they' as in 'I like these clothes. They look good on me', but not as in 'I like these people. They are friendly'.

fo can either refer to a group of people you are speaking to, or a mixture of people you are speaking to and people you are not speaking to. Likewise, the 'inclusive we' can refer to yourself plus the people you are speaking to or yourself plus the people you are speaking to plus others.

6.2 Reflexive pronouns

Reflexive pronouns are formed by adding the suffix *-ski*. For example, *naski* means 'myself'. There is also the word *kenta*, meaning 'each other'. This word is used in the same way as in English.

Unlike in English, *kōxō* has reflexive possessive determiners. A sentence such as 'he ate his food' would be ambiguous in English, as it could mean either 'he ate his own food' or 'he ate another person's food', however in *kōxō* the use of a reflexive possessive determiner is obligatory in the former case. So we have

kefo ga kô koif

eat.PST NOM.he his food

He ate his (another person's) food

kefo ga koski koif
eat.PST NOM.he his-REFL food
He ate his (own) food

There are also reflexive possessive determiners for it, they (animate) and they (inanimate).

7. Markers: part I

7.1 Introduction to markers

In *kōxō*, what in English are called 'prepositions', 'conjunctions' and 'conjunctive adverbs' are collectively called 'markers'.

Why the need for this reclassification? Consider the sentence 'I waited until tomorrow'. Clearly, 'until' is a preposition. But what about 'I waited until he came'? Here 'until' is acting more like a conjunction, joining two sentences together. But is it really joining two sentences, or is 'he came' just another argument of the verb? What about a sentence like 'I went to the shop for him'? Is 'for' marking an argument of the verb or is 'for him' being appended to the clause 'I went to the shop'? In reality, it makes no difference which interpretation is chosen.

We can also sometimes interpret markers as showing the relationship between phrases rather than linking to a verb or appending to the end of a sentence. For example, in the sentence 'if I do that, then I will feel good' the phrase 'I do that' is marked by 'if' and the phrase 'I will feel good' is marked by 'then' and these two markers show how the phrases relate to each other. This interpretation is valid even when one of the phrases is unmarked. For example, in the sentence 'I wanted to do it, therefore I did it' the main clause is unmarked. However, we could hypothetically invent a marker that marks the main clause. So again, the distinction between 'conjunctions' and 'conjunctive adverbs' is quite artificial, just as the distinction between 'prepositions' and 'conjunctions' is.

7.2 Using markers with the continuous aspect

Sentences that in English are formed using a marker with the copula are formed in *kōxō* by using the marker with the continuous aspect auxiliary verb. For example, in the English sentence 'the cup was under the table', we use 'was' (which is the past tense of the copula 'to be') with 'under'. In *kōxō*, the sentence is:

mo ze gup onde se tabl
CONT.PST NOM.se NOM.cup under se table

Here, the auxiliary verb *mē* is used in the past tense with *onde se tabl* acting as the predicate and *ze gup* acting as the subject.

7.3 Basic markers

The following is a list of basic markers.

kōxō	English
CASE MARKERS	
consonant mutation	nominative
MARKERS OF PLACE	
an	at
en	in
os	out
on	on
of	off
mus	from
me	to
ōve	over
onde	under, below
mose	between
masē	behind
kore	in front of (see notes)
fasi	in front of (see notes)
odi	against (see notes)
aki	against (see notes)
al	through
mori	around
sopō	beyond
faus	past (see notes)
nad	at the bottom of
pai	by, next to, beside
lan	along
eksi	near
mēhō	far away from
kevan	across
sen	away from (without motion)
esen	away from (with motion)
op	up
nan	down
MARKERS OF TIME	
edai	before
apsi	after
lā	as
momes	during, while
tul	since
ase	until
fan	for

are	in
enare	within
otse	ago
	as soon as
	as long as
pô	by (see notes)
	now that
OTHER MARKERS	
ha	topic marker
ev	of
med	with
ovi	without
eboi	to (see notes)
nen	with (instrumental)
opō	about (topic)
omi	about, approximately
ondō	against (see notes)
suton	except
olima	in accordance with
son	but (see notes)
elke	by (see notes)
meson	instead of
afel	out of (see notes)
safan	such as, for example
sē	like, as (see notes)
sū	as, than (see notes)
fisen	to (see notes)
li	by (passive marker)
fe	for (see notes)
oli	for (see notes)
ege	for (see notes)
kogen	for (see notes)
anan	up to
olo	although, even though
temō	therefore, so
ābe	however, but
	nevertheless, even so
	moreover, in addition
tapan	whereas
tumes	despite
	then (as in 'if...then...')

i	see 'relative clauses'
o	see 'relative clauses'
ide	see 'relative clauses'
ode	see 'relative clauses'
onas	see 'relative clauses'
odnas	see 'relative clauses'
mā	see notes
wā	nominative of <i>mā</i>
kauī	see notes
CONDITIONALS	
lē	if (possible)
lō	if (counterfactual)
noi lē	only if
noi lō	only if
IDENTIFIERS	
fê	where
fon	when
CORRELATIVE MARKERS	
	not only...but also
	just as...so...
	the...the...
	as...as...
	no sooner...than...
	not even...let alone
PHRASAL MARKERS	
on se top	on top of
an se top	at the top of

7.3.1 Notes on markers of place

faus

faus means 'past' as in 'I walked past it'.

pai

pai means 'by' as in 'I sat by the tree'. It is not to be confused with *li*, which is a translation of the 'by' found in passive sentences such as 'The food was eaten by the man'.

kore

A kore B means 'A in front of B' where A is turned away from B, rather than facing it. For example, 'I was in front of him in the queue'. It is not to be confused with *fasi*.

fasi

A *fasi* B means 'A in front of B' where A is facing B, rather than turned away from it. For example, 'I stood in front of the wall (facing it)'. It is not to be confused with *kore*.

odi

A *odi* B means 'A against B' where A is turned away from B rather than facing it. For example, 'I leaned (with my back) against the wall'. It is not to be confused with *ondō* or *aki*.

aki

A *aki* B means 'A against B' where A is facing B rather than turned away from it. For example, 'I pushed against the wall'. It is not to be confused with *odi* or *ondō*.

eksi

eksi means 'near' as in

mi xa eksi se fak

CONT.PRS NOM. I near se house

I am near the house

mi xa eksi

CONT.PRS NOM. I near

I am near

mēhō

mēhō means 'far away from' as in

mi xa mēhō se fak

CONT.PRS NOM. I far se house

I am far from the house

mi ze vak mēhō

CONT.PRS NOM. se NOM. house far

the house is far away

sen

sen means 'away from'. It refers to a static position rather than motion. For example, we can use *sen* to translate 'I stood away from him' but not 'I moved away from him'.

esen

esen means 'away from'. It refers to motion rather than a static position. For example, we can use *esen* to translate 'I moved away from him' but not 'I stood away from him'.

7.3.2 Notes on markers of time

lā

lā can be roughly translated as 'as'. It marks an action that occurs simultaneously with another over an extended period, as opposed to *dori* which can mark an instantaneous action that happens at some point during a longer action but does not last for a similarly long duration.

momes

momes can mean 'during' or 'while' – there is no distinction between the two in *kōxō*. For example, we can say

momes ando xa kefē
during PROG.PST NOM.I eat.INF
while I was eating

and

momes se korek
during se war
during the war

The clause after *momes* is in the null tense even if the clause before it is not. For example

kamo ga momes kefē xa
come.PST NOM.he while eat.INF NOM.I
He came while I ate

fan

fan means 'for' as in 'I lived there for three years'.

are

are means 'in' as in 'I will be there in three hours'.

enare

enare means 'in' as in 'I will be there within three hours'

otse

otse means 'ago'. Unlike in English, it is placed before what it marks, following the same pattern as all other markers. For example

otse toksu kabsen
ago three.SP year.PL
three years ago

pô

pô means 'by' as in 'he will be here by tomorrow'

7.3.3 Notes on miscellaneous markers

eboi

eboi is a 'static to' used to show a relational direction rather than a direction of motion. It is used in phrases such as 'correspond to', 'point to', 'refer to'.

nen

nen is used to mark something that is being used. For example

kefi xa sen nen ne fok
eat.PRS NOM.I it with ne fork
I eat it with a fork

In English, the word 'with' is used both for things that are together (as in 'I go with him') and the instrumental, but in *kōxō* a distinction is made between these, with the translation of the first 'with' being *med* and the second 'with' being *nen*.

opō

opō means 'about' in the sense of a topic e.g. 'the book is about science', but not in the sense of an estimation e.g. 'it weighs about...'

omi

omi means 'about' in the sense of an estimation e.g. 'it weighs about...', but not in the sense of a topic e.g. 'the book is about...'

ondō

ondō means 'against' as in 'I was against the proposal'. It is not to be confused with *odi* or *aki*.

son

son means 'but' as in 'it was not blue but red', not as in 'I like him, but he is annoying'.

elke

elke means 'by' or 'in order of', as in 'the children were arranged by age'.

afel

afel means 'out of' as in 'I chose out of the options' or 'Three out of five were blue', but not as in 'he came out of the house'.

safan

safan means 'such as' or 'for example'. The nominalisation of *safan* is *safanus*, which means 'example'.

sē

sē means 'like' as in 'margarine is like butter'. It also means 'as' as in 'he is as big as me'. It should not be confused with *sū*, which can also be translated as 'as'.

sū

sū means 'as' as in 'I think of him as a friend'. It also means 'than' as in 'he is bigger than me'. It should not be confused with *sē*, which can also be translated as 'as'.

fisen

fisen is a translation of the 'to' that is used to describe perspective, as in 'It looks big to me' (i.e. it looks big from my perspective). It should not be used to translate sentences like 'I'm going to the shop' or 'I want to eat'.

li

li is the translation of the 'by' found in passive sentences such as 'the food was eaten by the man'. Not to be confused with *bai* or *bā*.

fe

fe is a translation of 'for' or 'for the benefit of'. For example, it is used to translate 'this is for you', 'I did it for you', 'I work for the company' and 'provide for'.

oli

oli means 'for' or 'in favour of' as in 'I am for the new law'. It is used to translate phrases such as 'vote for' and 'fight for'.

ege

ege is a translation of 'for' used to describe how something is relative to others of the same category. For example, 'he is active for an old man'.

kogen

kogen means 'for' or 'in exchange for'. It can be used to mark something given as payment for something positive e.g. 'I gave him a coin for the apple', but it could also mark something given as exchange for something negative e.g. 'he was punished for his crime'.

anan

anan means 'up to' as in 'it will take up to three hours' or 'it can hold up to two litres'.

tumes

tumes means 'despite' or 'in spite of'. *tumes sen* means 'despite it', 'in spite of it' or 'anyway'.

kau

kau is used to translate 'that' in phrases such as 'the possibility that...' and 'the idea that...' *kau* is often omitted. For example, we could translate 'the possibility that it will happen' either as

se kanosus kau korasi zen
se possible.us kau happen.FUT NOM.it

or simply

se kanosus korasi zen
se possible.us happen.FUT NOM.it

Note: Some might argue that there is no need for *kau* because *mā* can be used to translate 'that' in such phrases. This is incorrect. I will now show why *mā* would not be an appropriate translation using examples.

Consider the phrase

kaki ze wan se puk
write.PRS NOM.se NOM.man se book
the man writes the book

We can turn this phrase into 'the writer of the book' using *ka i*. (This construction is covered in more detail in section 14.6). We get

ka i kaki se puk
he NOM.o write.PRS se book

ka i kaki se puk is se man i.e. the whole phrase is equal to what was in the nominative before applying *i*.

Now consider the phrase

kaikimi xa kamasi ga mā kiū kamasi ga
disagree.PRS NOM.I come.FUT NOM.he mā not.ADV come.FUT NOM.he
I disagree that he will come, believing instead that he will not come

Using *sen i*, we get

sen i kaikimi xa mā kiū kamasi ga
it NOM.o disagree.PRS NOM.I mā not.ADV come.FUT NOM.he
the thing I disagree on, thinking instead that he will not come

So again, the resultant phrase is equal to what was originally marked by the accusative marker. 'The thing I disagree with, thinking instead that he will not come' is 'that he will come'. *sen i kaikimi xa* is not what is marked by *mā*. In fact, in this particular case, it is the opposite, since *sen i kaikimi xa* is what you disagree with and what is marked by *mā* is the opposite opinion, which is what you actually think.

So, returning to one of the original examples, translating 'the possibility that...' as *se kanosai mā...* is incorrect because what is marked by *mā* is not equal to *se kanosai*.

7.3.4 Notes on conditionals

lē and *lō*

lē and *lō* are the two translations of 'if' in *kōxō*. Usage of *lē* indicates that the clause to which it is applied may be true, or at least that the speaker is entertaining the idea that it might be true. Usage of *lō* implies that the clause to which it is applied is definitely not true. For example:

lē feli ga kamē, kamasi ga
lē want.PRS NOM.he come.INF, come.FUT NOM.he
if he wants to come, he will

lō feli ga kamē, foi ga
lō want.PRS NOM.he come.INF, would.PRS NOM.he
if he wanted to come, he would

lē felo ga kamē, kāmōt kiū kamo ga?
lē want.PST NOM.he come.INF, why not.ADV come.PST NOM.he
if he wanted to come, why didn't he?

lō felo ga kamē, foi ga
lō want.PST NOM.he come.INF, would.PRS NOM.he
if he had wanted to come, he would have

Using *lē* or *lō* with the null tense indicates a condition that is generally true without reference to a particular time. For example:

lē misanē xeves ne safek, fugnasi zen
lē water.INF SP.someone ne plant, grow.FUT NOM.it
if one waters a plant, it will grow

lē can be marked for case. For example:

kiū keni xa s'lē kamasi ga
not.ADV know.PRS NOM.I ACC-lē come.FUT NOM.he
I don't know whether he will come

From *lē* and *lō* other expressions can be formed, such as:

mot lē, mot lō = what if?
sū lē, sū lō = as if
fe lē = in case

noi lē, noi lō

noi lē and *noi lō* are both translations of 'only if'. These are often used where we would use 'unless' in English, which has no direct translation in *kōxō*. For example:

feli xa kinē noi lē...
want.PRS NOM.I go.INF only la...
'I want to go only if...' or 'I don't want to go unless...'

kamo xa noi lō felo vu mā sen
come.PST NOM.I only lō want.PST NOM.you mā it
I would have come only if you had wanted me to

7.3.5 Notes on the marker *mā*

The marker *mā* is worthy of separate treatment since it has no direct translation in English. It has a nominative and a plain form, with the plain form sometimes functioning as a normal marker (we call this its non-case usage) and sometimes acting almost as a case marker, marking something that is similar to the accusative but not quite the same, which we call the supplementary accusative.

Let us first see examples of *mā* marking the supplementary accusative, comparing it to the same sentence where the accusative is used (i.e. where there is no marking, since the accusative is not marked in *kōxō*) to illustrate what the difference between them is.

somani xa kinē ga
perceive.PRS NOM.I go.INF NOM.he
I perceive him going

somani xa mā kini ga
perceive.PRS NOM.I mā go.PRS NOM.he
I perceive that he is going

miri xa kinē ga
see.PRS NOM.I go.INF NOM.he
I see him going

miri xa mā kini ga
see.PRS NOM.I mā go.PRS NOM.he
I see that he is going

kansi xa sā sigai
determine.PRS NOM.I sā win.ai
I determine the winner

kansi xa mā mē ga se sigai
determine.PRS NOM.I mā be.PRS NOM.he se win.ai
I determine that he is the winner

However, it should not be assumed that *mā* simply means 'that'. The following examples refute this:

connection between *mā* and spec./subspec. distinction. 'solar eclipses are completely predictable' --> completely predictable *mā* na solar eclipse ???

lesko xa nô lev
risk.PST NOM.I my life
I risked my life

lesko xa mā osvendē ga
risk.PST NOM.I mā find.out.PST NOM.he
I risked him finding out

fāli xa ne kād
choose.PRS NOM.I ne card
I choose a card

fāli xa mā ne kād
choose.PRS NOM.I mā ne card
I choose a card (out of a set including things that are not cards)

polti xa ne sairaxo
plan.PRS NOM.I ne travel-NZ
I plan a journey

polti xa mā ne sairaxo
plan.PRS NOM.I mā ne travel-NZ
I plan (on going on) a journey

fetsi xa sen
affect.PRS NOM.I it
I affect it

fetsi xa mā sen
affect.PRS NOM.I mā it
I cause it

Now let us see examples of *mā* in its non-case usage. Such sentences can often be paired with a sentence where *mā* is being used to mark the supplementary accusative, as shown below:

Example 1:

tigasmī xa ka mā paro sen
accuse.PRS NOM.I he mā do.PST it
I accuse him of doing it

tigasmi xa mā paro ga sen
accuse.PRS NOM.I mā do.PST NOM.he it
I accuse that/ make the allegation that he did it

Example 2:

kati xa mā mi ga kud
think.PRS NOM.I mā CONT.PRS NOM.he good
I think that he is good

kati xa ka mā kud
think.PRS NOM.I he mā good
I think him good

Example 3:

kaikimi xa soli wen
disagree.PRS NOM.I should.PRS NOM.we
I disagree that we should (i.e. 'I don't think we should')

kaikimi xa mā kiū soli wen
disagree.PRS NOM.I mā not.ADV should.PRS NOM.we
I disagree, my opinion being that we should not

kaikimi xa soli wen mā kiū soli wen
disagree.PRS NOM.I should.PRS NOM.we mā not.ADV should.PRS NOM.we
I disagree that we should, thinking instead that we should not

Sometimes, the non-case usage of *mā* occurs even though there is no corresponding phrase involving the supplementary accusative. For example:

mi xa tames mā kamo ga
CONT.PRS NOM.I happy mā come.PST NOM.he
I am happy that he came

Sentences involving the nominative form of *mā*, *wā*, are typically either passive (and hence intransitive) sentences that can be paired with a sentence that uses the supplementary accusative, as in

Example 1:

mi wā kamasi ga kansad

CONT.PRS NOM.mā *come.FUT NOM.he determine.PASS*
It is determined that he will come

kansi xa mā kamasi ga
determine.PRS NOM.I mā come.FUT NOM.he
I determine that he will come

Example 2:

mi wā kamasi ga poltad
CONT.PRS NOM.mā come.FUT NOM.he plan.PASS
It is planned that he will come

polti xa mā kamasi ga
plan.PRS NOM.I mā come.FUT NOM.he
I plan that he will come

or they are sentences that can be paired with sentences involving the non-case usage of *mā*, as in

anmiri wā mi zen neso
look.PRS NOM.mā CONT.PRS NOM.it easy
It looks like it is easy

anmiri zen mā neso
look.PRS NOM.it mā easy
It looks easy

8. Relative clauses

Kōxō uses relative pronouns to form relative clauses. Relative pronouns are inflected for case. For example:

se man i miro na
se man NOM.o *see.PST I*
the man that saw me

se man o miro xa
se man o *see.PST NOM.I*
the man that I saw

se fak en o fōni xa
se house in o live.PRS NOM.I
the house I live in

Kōxō distinguishes between restrictive and non-restrictive relative clauses. There are therefore restrictive and non-restrictive relative pronouns, shown below:

	restrictive		non-restrictive	
	short	long	short	long
nom.	i	onas	ide	odnas
plain	o		ode	

For example:

se man ide fōni sē
se man ide live.PRS there
the man, who lives there

se man i fōni sē
se man NOM.o *live.PRS there*
the man who lives there

The difference between these two phrases is that in the first the man has already been referred to (although this is not shown) so that the man we are referring to when we say 'the man' is already fixed. The clause *ide fōni sē* is then giving extra information about the man. In the second phrase the man we are referring to has not yet been fixed and it is the clause *i fōni sē* that specifies which man we are referring to.

Relative pronouns in kōxō do not take account of animacy, unlike in English in which we would say 'the thing that...' but could say 'the man who...'

A free relative clause can be formed with *sa* or *ka*. For example:

sen o miro xa
it o see.PST NOM.I
what I saw

ka o miro xa
he o see.PST NOM.I
who I saw

The long forms are used in more complicated sentences where the short forms cannot be used. They can be translated as 'such that'. For example, we would struggle to translate a phrase such as 'the people to whose country I travelled and lived with them' using the short forms, since two different markers are involved. Even in English, such a phrase sounds somewhat wrong. It is far better in such situations to use the long forms, so that the phrase becomes something like 'the people such that I travelled to their country and lived with them'.

different specificity levels of *sen*? e.g. subspecific 'that which...'

Relativisers help to reduce ambiguity. For example, in English the phrase 'simplifying assumptions' could refer to the act of simplifying one's assumptions or an assumption that simplifies, but in kōxō this ambiguity is not present. We have

sampamē ongaton
simplify.INF assumption

ongaton i sampamē
assumption i simplify.INF

To give another example, 'I hate controlling people' could mean 'I hate people who are controlling' or 'I hate to control people'. But this ambiguity is resolved in kōxō.

9. Adjectives and the coda form

In kōxō, adjectives come before nouns.

Both adjectives and adverbs **and verbs** in kōxō have two forms - the coda and non-coda form.

The coda form is used for adjectives at the end of adjectival phrases. For example:

se kē feden kude man
se not usual good.COD man
the unusually good man

Here, there is adverb ('not') and two adjectives ('usual' and 'good'). Together they form an adjectival phrase, 'unusually good'. However, only the final word, 'good', is in the coda form. This eliminates ambiguity by delineating one adjectival phrase from another. For example, we could also have

se kiu feden kude man
se not.ADV usual good.COD man
the not usually good man (i.e. the man who is not usually good)

se kē fedne kude man
se not usual.COD good.COD man
the unusual, good man

The coda form is also used in predicates. For example:

mi ze wan kē feden kude
CONT.PRS NOM.se NOM.man not usual good.COD
the man is unusually good

In practice, this means that adjectives are in coda form most of the time.

Adverbs also have coda forms, and the coda forms of quantifiers are determiners. This will be dealt with in the relevant sections.

10. Determiners

10.1 The topic marker *ha*

In order to properly understand specificity, which is one of the properties of determiners in *kōxō*, we must first introduce the topic marker *ha*.

Consider the sentence 'I don't want a specific book'. In English, this sentence is ambiguous. It could either mean 'I don't want a specific book (although I may still want a book without having a specific one in mind)' or 'there is a specific book that I don't want'.

In *kōxō*, the first of these interpretations is translated as

kiū feli xa ne puk
not.ADV want.PRS NOM.I ne book

To translate the second, we use the topic marker *ha*. The translation is

ha ne puk, kiū feli xa sen
ha ne book, not.ADV want.PRS NOM.I it

Literally this means 'regarding a certain book, I do not want it'.

10.2 Specificity

As well as being inflected for definiteness, articles (and some other determiners) in *kōxō* are declined for specificity. We will first explain the different levels of specificity and how they are used before listing the different inflections for each determiner.

10.2.1 Specific articles

Specific articles are used to refer to something specific. The specific indefinite article is *ne*. The specific definite article is *se*.

An example of *se* being used is:

andi xa sokē me se nêkudus
PROG.PRS NOM.I search.INF to se most-good.us
I'm looking for the best (and it is known who the best is)

Examples of *ne* being used include:

feli xa ne puk

want.PRS NOM.I ne book
I want a (specific) book/ There is a book I want

feli xa ne puken
want NOM.I ne book.PL
I want some (specific) books/ There are some books I want

fādi xa ne pus
wait.PRS NOM.I ne bus
I'm waiting for a (specific) bus

10.2.2 Subspecific articles

In the previous section, articles were defined that are used to refer to something specific. There are also articles that are used when we do not want to refer to something specific. For reasons that will be explained later, these are called 'subspecific articles'.

The subspecific indefinite article is *nā*. The subspecific definite article is *sā*.

Examples for *nā* include:

feli xa nā puk
want.PRS NOM.I nā book
I want a book (but I do not have a specific book in mind)

feli xa nā puken
want.PRS NOM.I nā book.PL
I want some books (but I do not have specific books in mind)

fādi xa nā pus
wait.PRS NOM.I nā bus
I'm waiting for a bus (I'll get on whichever one comes next. I don't care where it takes me.)

These articles are often used to form gnomic sentences (i.e. sentences that make generalisations). For example:

paukê xā dog
bark.HAB.PRS NOM.nā NOM.dog
dogs bark

tovê xā dog nā kat

chase.HAB.PRS NOM.nā NOM.dog nā cat
dogs chase cats

magi xa nā tog
like.PRS NOM.I nā dog
I like dogs

Examples for *sā* include:

andi xa sokē me sā nêkudus
PROG.PRS NOM.I search.INF to sā most-good.us
I'm looking for the best (and it has not been decided who the best is)

sā is also used in contexts such as

kɪnmeko ga sā computer
invent.PST NOM.he sā computer
he invented the computer

The plural form is used in phrases such as 'the Germans' (the German people, not specific Germans), 'humanity' (the humans), 'the workers' (the working class, not specific workers) etc.

10.2.3 Superspecific articles

When an article and its noun phrase are 'invoked' at one level of nesting before the clause in which they are referred to, we say they have a scope level of 1. This is in contrast to simpler sentences such as those discussed in the previous section, where they have scope level 0. For example:

ha ne puk kiu feli xa sen
TOP ne book not.ADV want.PRS NOM.I it
There is a book that I don't want

The above sentence literally means 'regarding a book, I don't want it'. 'A book' is invoked at one level of nesting before the clause in which we refer to it, and so it has a scope level of 1. This is in contrast to

kiu feli xa ne puk
not.ADV want.PRS NOM.I ne book
I don't want a specific book

where *ne puk* has a scope level of 0. As discussed previously, there is a subtle difference in meaning in these two sentences. The first means 'There is a book that I don't want', the second means 'I do not have a book in mind that I want, but may still want a book without having decided which one'. The sentence 'I don't want a specific book' is ambiguous in English without extensive explanation. Simply saying 'I don't want a specific book' could be interpreted as having either of these meanings.

Sentences such as *ha ne puk kiu feli xa sen* are so common that we define a new article, *ni*, to simplify its structure. Using this article,

ha ne puk kiu feli xa sen

becomes

kiu feli xa ni puk
not.ADV want.PRS NOM.I ni book

For reasons that will be explained later, we call this article 'superspecific'. There is also a superspecific definite article, *si*.

Let us look at another example of the superspecific indefinite article:

lē mosti vu kaufē ni puken
if must.PRS NOM.you buy.INF ni book.PL

This sentence means 'if you have to buy a specific book (as opposed to being allowed to choose which book you want)'. We can change the meaning of this sentence by lowering or raising the scope level, and in a later section we will come back to this example to see how each scope level affects its meaning.

Another use of superspecific articles is shown below:

kato ga mā mē zi rugim fassen
think.PST NOM.he mā CONT NOM.si NOM.lie true
He thought the lie was true

Here, a superspecific article is used with the word for 'lie' because the person in question did not think it was a lie. It would not make sense to think it was a lie and that it was true. A final example:

teldo ga pare nivot kē kanose

try.PST NOM.he do.INF something.SPSP not possible.COD
He tried to do something impossible

Here, we use the superspecific to mean 'the thing he tried to do was impossible' rather than 'he tried to do something impossible (not a specific thing)' which is somewhat nonsensical and hence in English would usually be rejected as an interpretation by context.

Yet another use of superspecific articles is in 'circular explanative phrases' (CEPs). Examples of such phrases include:

'why I am who I am'
'why is America called America?'
'why do I look the way I look?'
'I like what I like because...'

Consider, for example, the third of these phrases – 'why do I look the way I look?' There are two interpretations of this question. The answer to the first of these would be something like 'it is logically impossible for you to not look the way you look. How can you not look like yourself?' In English, we know that this is not the intended meaning of the question, because it is pointless to ask such a question. The second interpretation is the common sense interpretation of the question. In *kōxō*, the translation of the first interpretation is

kāmōt anmiri xa lau laue anmiri xa
because.what look.PRS NOM.I how how.NZ look.PRS NOM.I

The translation of the second interpretation uses a superspecific article:

kāmōt anmiri xa lau si laue anmiri xa
because.what look.PRS NOM.I how si how.NZ look.PRS NOM.I

In examples that do not involve a determiner, such as 'why is America called America?', we would use a specificity prefix instead.

10.2.4 Specificity level and nesting level

As discussed, superspecific articles usually indicate a topic marker one level of nesting before the position at which it is used. However, sometimes a superspecific article may indicate a topic marker at more than level of nesting behind its position. This is because the actual rule is that it indicates a topic marker at the next level of nesting that makes a difference in meaning. For example

kiū feli xa ne puk
not.ADV want.PRS NOM.I ne book

means the same as

kiū ha ne puk feli xa sen
not.ADV ha ne book want.PRS NOM.I it

so

kiū feli xa ni puk
not.ADV want.PRS NOM.I ni book

does not mean

kiū ha ne puk feli xa sen
not.ADV ha ne book want.PRS NOM.I it

Instead,

kiū feli xa ni puk
not.ADV want.PRS NOM.I ni book

means

ha ne puk kiū feli xa sen
ha ne book not.ADV want.PRS NOM.I it

10.2.5 Nesting by other grammatical elements

We have seen various ways in which a phrase can be nested. For example we saw that in the sentence

lē mosti vu kaufē ni puken
if must.PRS NOM.you buy.INF ni book.PL

kaufē ni puke is nested by the accusative case, although this is unmarked. We have also seen that phrases can be nested by an adverb or some other element of the sentence. For example, in the aforementioned example, *lē* also nests, and we saw that in the sentence

kiū feli xa ne puk

not.ADV want.PRS NOM.I ne book

feli xa ne puk is nested by *kiu*. We now give a more comprehensive treatment of which elements can nest phrases and the effect they have on specificity level.

Firstly, it should be noted that the accusative case is not the only grammatical element that can nest. Basic markers as well as the relative clause markers can also nest. For example, in the sentence

kino xa me se sop fe kaufē nevoj
go.PST NOM.I to se shop fe buy.INF SP.something
I went to the shop to buy something'

kaufē nevoj is nested inside *fe*, so *nevoj* does not refer to a specific thing. And in the sentence

feli xa nā fak i tai ne kāden
want.PRS NOM.I nā house NOM.o have.PRS ne garden
I want a house that has a garden

tai ne kāden is nested inside *i*, so *ne kāden* does not refer to a specific garden. the table below summarises the effect of various grammatical elements on specificity level:

Grammatical element coming before or forming part of verb	Specificity level affected?
marker	yes
imperative mood	yes
future tense	yes
other tenses	no
kiū	yes
other 'miscellaneous' adverbs	no
adverbs of mood	yes
aspect (except perfect)	no
perfect aspect	yes
adverbs of degree	no
adverbs of comparison	no
adverbs of frequency	yes
adverbs of time (except 'about to', 'again', already,	no

still, no longer)	
about to, again, already, still??. no longer??	yes

modal verbs such as *mostē* etc.

10.2.6 Articles with higher levels of specificity

Determiners with higher levels of specificity are possible but do not have morphologically distinct forms. Instead, we indicate levels of specificity beyond the superspecific by prefixing the determiner with the specificity prefix *min-*. This increases the specificity level by one. Reiterating this prefix further increases the specificity level. For example, *minmin-* raises the specificity level by two.

We could use *min* to form the superspecific. For example, we could use *minne* as the superspecific indefinite article, but because the indefinite article already has a superspecific form, *ni*, there is no need to use *minne*. However, there are many words that infrequently need to be used in the superspecific, so their superspecific form is formed using *min* rather than having a completely separate one like *ni*.

One class of words for which *min* is always used to form the superspecific is proper nouns. We have already seen situations where we would need the superspecific form of a proper noun in section 10.1. For example, the sentence ‘why is America called America?’ translates to

ha merekie, kāmot mi zen kalad mā merekie?
ha America, kā-what CONT.PRS NOM.it call.PASS mā America?

We can use *min* to rewrite this as *kāmot mi winmerekie kalad mā merekie?*

In addition to the specificity prefix *min*, which raises the specificity level, I define the prefix *mom* to be the prefix that lowers specificity by 1. This would be used to convert a specific form to a subspecific form, although I am yet to come across a situation where this would be used.

10.2.7 Compound specificity

Consider the sentence

kiū feli xa ne puk
not.ADV want.PRS NOM.I ne book

This means 'I do not want a specific book (but I may want a book without wanting a specific one)'. In other words, it is possible for

kiū feli xa ne puk
not.ADV want.PRS NOM.I ne book

and

feli xa nā puk
want.PRS NOM.I nā book

to be true simultaneously. Similarly, we can say

kiū feli xa nā puk. feli xa ne puk.
not.ADV want.PRS NOM.I nā book. want.PRS NOM.I ne book

which roughly translates to 'I don't want just any book. I want a specific book' (I say 'roughly' because *nā* does not indicate that absolutely any book would be suitable, and there is in fact a separate word for 'any'). To say 'I don't want a book (at all)', we could say

kiū feli xa ne puk wa kiū feli xa nā puk
not.ADV want.PRS NOM.I ne book and not.ADV want.PRS NOM.I nā book

but this is long-winded. So, we introduce a compound indefinite article, *memne*, that combines *ne* and *nā*. Formally, the definition of *memne* is *ne tê nā*, where *tê* is the translation of the Boolean OR. So, instead of saying

kiū feli xa ne puk wā kiū feli xa nā puk
not.ADV want.PRS NOM.I ne book and not.ADV want.PRS NOM.I nā book

we can just say

kiū feli xa memne puk
not.ADV want.PRS NOM.I memne book

memne is not only used in negative phrases, such as those involving *kiū*, and should certainly not be thought of as equivalent to the English word 'no' as in 'I want no books'. For example

lē feli vu memne puk
lē want.PRS NOM.you wemne book

means 'if you want a book (whether it be a specific one or you do not have one in mind)'.

In general, compound articles can be formed using the specificity prefix *mem-*. For example **XXX**

10.2.8 Specificity, scope, and the non-substitution principle

There are two different ways of interpreting the specificity of determiners. One is to apply what I call the 'non-substitution principle', and the other is not to apply it.

The non-substitution principle

The non-substitution principle is the idea that it is not true that noun phrases with a specific determiner can be 'substituted' with the specific thing they represent without changing the meaning of the sentence. Let us look at an example of how a sentence would be interpreted when the non-substitution principle applies and when it does not apply. Consider the sentence:

kiu feli xa ne puk
not.ADV want.PRS NOM.I ne book

If the non-substitution principle does not apply, we assume the speaker of this sentence has a specific book in mind that is not stated in the sentence, and hence '*ne puk*' can be substituted with this specific book without changing the meaning of the sentence. We might say that in the sentence '*ne puk*' has a hidden identity. So, say the book was *The Catcher in the Rye*. Then the meaning of the sentence would be 'I don't want *The Catcher in the Rye*'. Of course, sometimes we may use *ne puk* twice in one sentence to refer to two different books, in which case one instance of *ne puk* would be equal to the first book and the other instance would be equal to the other book.

If the non-substitution principle does apply, then there is no book that '*ne puk*' can be substituted with, and the interpretation of the sentence is 'I don't want a specific book' (i.e. I don't have a book in mind that I want, but may still want a book without having decided which I want).

All of this begs the question of whether one of these interpretations of specificity is correct. In other words, does it matter whether we choose to construct a language in which the non-substitution principle applies or one in which it does not apply? The answer is that we should apply the non-substitution principle,

since problems arise in a language that does not use this principle, whereas if we do apply this principle these problems are solved.

As an example, consider the following sentence

lē mosti vu kaufē ne puken
if must.PRS NOM.you buy.INF ne book.PL

Here, the article *ne* has a scope level of 0. Under the non-substitution principle, the interpretation of this sentence is 'If you have to buy books' (not specific books). Now consider the sentence

lē mosti vu kaufē ni puken
if must.PRS NOM.you buy.INF ni book.PL

Here, the article *ni* has a scope level of 1. Under the non-substitution principle, the interpretation of this sentence is 'if you have to buy specific books' (i.e. if it has been specified which books you have to buy). And finally, consider the sentence

lē mosti vu kaufē minni puken
if must.PRS NOM.you buy.INF min-ni book.PL

Here, the article *minni* has a scope level of 2. Under the non-substitution principle, the interpretation of this sentence is 'there are certain books such that if you have to buy them...'

We may now ask whether we can construct sentences with each of these interpretations if the non-substitution principle does not apply. The answer is no. We can construct a sentence using the first interpretation using a non-specific article:

lē mosti vu kaufē nā puken
if must.PRS NOM.you buy.INF nā book.PL

We can construct a sentence with the third interpretation using a specific article

lē mosti vu kaufē ne puken
if must.PRS NOM.you buy.INF ne book.PL

since when the non-substitution principle does not apply, noun phrases with specific articles take on maximum scope. However, we cannot construct a sentence with the second interpretation.

A proposed solution to the problem

One solution that could be proposed is to use a **premarker** indicating that substitution does not apply to the phrase the premarker is applied to. So, if we call the premarker X, a sentence with the second interpretation in a language where the non-substitution does not apply would be

lē mosti vu kaufē Xne puken
if must.PRS NOM.you buy.INF X-ACC-ne book.PL

However, this proposal ultimately does not solve the problem. In the example we have been using, there are three possible scope levels. Let us derive a more complicated example from this i.e. one with four possible scope levels. The example is shown below with indications of their interpretations under the non-substitution principle.

lē kiu mosti vu kaufē ne puk
if not.ADV must.PRS NOM.you buy.INF ne book
if you don't have to buy a book (at all)

lē kiu mosti vu kaufē ni puk
if not.ADV must.PRS NOM.you buy.INF ni book
if you don't have to buy a specific book

lē kiu mosti vu kaufē minni puk
if not.ADV must.PRS NOM.you buy.INF wan-ni book
if you don't have to buy a given book/ if there is a book that you don't have to buy
(then you don't need to make a note of its ISBN)

lē kiu mosti vu kaufē minminni puk
if not.ADV must.PRS NOM.you buy.INF min-min-ni book
there is a book such that if you don't have to buy it (you will save a lot of money
because it is expensive)

Now we ask whether, in a language where the non-substitution principle does not apply and we may use the 'X' premarker we defined earlier, we can construct clauses with all four of these interpretations.

As before, using a non-specific article would give us the first interpretation, and using a specific article would give us the final interpretation (i.e. the fourth) since it takes on maximum scope. If we apply the premarker, we get the second interpretation. But it is not clear how we would get the third. Unlike the prefix *min* that is used under the non-substitution principle, chaining multiple Xs together will do nothing. If X suspends substitution, then it can be used once. Once we have stated that substitution is not allowed, stating it again makes no difference.

So even with the premarker, we cannot construct clauses for each of these interpretations in a language where the non-substitution principle does not hold. Hence we discard both the proposed solution of the premarker and the idea of using a language where the non-substitution principle does not apply, and accept that we must use the non-substitution principle.

10.2.9 The relationship between specificity and scope

There seems to be a connection between specificity and scope. Consider the following pair of phrases:

feli vu nā puk
want.PRS NOM.you nā book

feli vu kaufē ne puk
want.PRS NOM.you buy.INF ne book

In the first phrase, a non-specific article is used. In the second, a specific article is used, but because the clause *kaufē ne puk* is nested, the noun phrase *ne puk* does not refer to something specific. In both cases, the subject wants a book but may not have a specific book in mind.

feli vu ne puk
want.PRS NOM.you ne book

feli vu kaufē ni puk
want.PRS NOM.you buy.INF ni book

In the first phrase, a specific article with scope of 0 is used. In the second phrase, the article has scope of 1. In both cases, the subject has a specific book in mind that they want. Returning to the previous pair of phrases and comparing it to this pair, we may propose that just as the second phrase in this pair has an article that is one scope level higher than in the first phrase, the second phrase in the first pair has an article that is one scope level higher than the first phrase

in the first pair, which would mean that *nā* has a scope level of -1, and hence that non-specificity is really just a scope level of -1 and hence that scope and specificity are really the same thing. It is due to this scope level of -1 that we use the term 'subspecific' rather than 'non-specific'.

The problem with this proposition is that it is disputable whether we can justify the idea that *ne puk* in *feli vu kaufē ne puk* is in some sense 'non-specific'. After all, it uses a specific article, so in what sense can we state formally that it is 'non-specific'? Our sense of it being non-specific may just be an intuition that is incorrect.

In fact, we can formalise this notion that *ne puk* in *feli vu kaufē ne puk* is in some sense 'non-specific'. To do this, we introduce a distinction between relative and absolute scope. Absolute scope is the sort of scope we have been dealing with up to this point - the scope of an article relative to its own location. But an article also has scope relative to other locations within the sentence. So, in *feli vu kaufē ne puk*, *ne puk* has scope of zero relative to its own location i.e. within the clause *kaufē ne puk*. However, it has scope of -1 relative to the verb *feli*, which explains its similarity in scope between *nā puk* in *feli nā puk*.

An invalid proof that non-specificity and scope of -1 are the same

There is seemingly an alternative proof to the idea that non-specificity and scope of -1 are the same which involves comparing language in which the non-substitution principle holds and language in which it does not hold. It is worth stating this proof and pointing out why it is invalid, arriving at the correct conclusion for the wrong reasons.

The argument is as follows. Consider a pair of sentences such as the following:

feli xa pālē xe wenek
want.PRS NOM.I speak.INF NOM.ne NOM.person

feli xa pālē xi wenek
want.PRS NOM.I speak.INF NOM.ni NOM.person

When the non-substitution principle applies, the first sentence means 'I want someone to speak (not a specific person)' and the second sentence means 'I want a specific person to speak'. If the non-substitution principle did not apply, the sentences with these interpretations would, respectively, be

feli xa pālē xā wenek
want.PRS NOM.I speak.INF NOM.nā NOM.person

feli xa pālē xe wenek
want.PRS NOM.I speak.INF NOM.ne NOM.person

We know that *ni* in the second sentence in the first pair is one specificity level higher than *ne* in the second sentence in the second pair, so we conclude that *nā* in the first sentence in the second pair is one specificity level higher than *ne* in the first sentence in the first pair. We know that *ne* has a specificity level (or scope level, if you prefer, of 0), so *nā* must have a specificity level of -1.

This argument is very similar to the argument given in the previous section for why *nā* has specificity of -1 but, unlike that argument, is incorrect. It appears to work in the example provided because there are only two scope levels available. But, as mentioned before, suspending the non-substitution principle causes specific articles to take on maximum scope. We saw this earlier in the example

lē mosti vu kaufē ne puken
if must.PRS NOM.you buy ne book.PL

where suspending the non-substitution principle gives the sentence the interpretation that

lē mosti vu kaufē minni puken
if must.PRS NOM.you buy min-ni book.PL

would have under the non-substitution principle, which is an increase of not one, but two scope levels.

10.3 Distributivity

Many determiners are declined for distributivity as well as specificity. Distributivity is indicated by prefixing the final vowel of the determiner with *x*. For example:

tai xulxu wenek ne torad
have.PRS NOM.all.SP.DIST NOM.person ne bike
everyone has a bike

Here, the determiner 'all' in 'all people' has been distributed so that the sentence means 'everyone has a (different) bike' and not 'everyone has the same bike'.

It may seem that we could do without distributivity in the above example, and that the meaning of the sentence is clear from context. However, distributivity becomes important in more complex examples. For example:

tai xāxe transistor tonō I-V curves
have.PRS NOM.nā.DIST NOM.transistor many.SP I-V curves
a given transistor has many I-V curves

In the above example, the subspecific indefinite article has been distributed. This may seem strange, since the noun phrase being distributed is singular. However, the idea is that since the article is subspecific, it is not referring to a specific thing and it can hence be distributed over all possible cases. It is analogous to the previous example, in which 'all' was distributed, and using 'all' in this example instead of *nā* would give essentially the same meaning except that the latter would be formulated using a generalised thing - *nā transistor* - and the former would be formulated using a set - *nulu transistor* (although the non-distributed versions do have different meanings).

Distributivity can be applied to one or multiple determiners in a sentence. Consider the following examples:

pālê dono wenken tonō pālonen
speak.HAB NOM.many.SP NOM.person.PL many.SP language.PL

pālê donxo wenken tonō pālonen
speak.HAB NOM.many.SP.DIST NOM.person.PL many.SP language.PL

pālê dono wenken tonxo pālonen
speak.HAB NOM.many.SP NOM.person.PL many.SP.DIST language.PL

pālê donxo wenken tonxo pālonen
speak.HAB NOM.many.SP.DIST NOM.person.PL many.SP.DIST language.PL

In each of these examples, a different combination of determiners are distributed. In the first, none are distributed. In the second, the first 'many' is distributed. In the third, the second 'many' is distributed. In the fourth, both the first and second 'many' are distributed.

The first example means many people each speak the same group of many languages. The second example means that there are many people who each speak many languages, and the languages spoken by one person may be different from the languages spoken by another. The third example is best

translated into the passive voice - 'many languages are spoken by many people'. It means that there are many languages that are each spoken by a (possibly different) group of many people. The final example means 'there are many languages and many people speak them'. In this example, it could be that each language is spoken by only one person, but the total number of people and the total number of languages is many.

diagram

In all of these examples, 'many' is specific. But there are examples where 'many' would need to be both distributed and superspecific. For example, consider the following sentences:

neso lenatê zen li nā menk i pālê tono pālonen
easy learn.PASS.HAB NOM.it by nā person.CNS NOM.o speak.HAB many.SP
language.PL

neso lenatê zen li nā menk i pālê tenxe pālonen
easy learn.PASS.HAB NOM.it by nā person.CNS NOM.o speak.HAB many.SPSP.DIST
language.PL

The first sentence does not use distribution, and means 'it is easily learned by a person who speaks many languages' i.e. 'if a person speaks many languages, regardless of what those languages are, it is easy for them to learn it'.

The second sentence means 'it is easily learned by people who speak many languages' i.e. 'there are many languages such that speaking it will make it easy to learn'. It differs grammatically from the first in that 'many' is distributed and the superspecific form of 'many' is used rather than the specific form. We use the superspecific form of 'many' to indicate that we are referring to a specific set of languages and not just stating that if a person speaks many languages, it will be easy to learn regardless which languages they are. We must then distribute 'many' because using a superspecific 'many' without distributing it would mean that a person must speak all of these languages to make it easy to learn.

10.4 Demonstratives

The following table shows the demonstratives – translations of 'this' and 'that'. The demonstratives only have specific forms. **Other forms can be formed using the appropriate prefix.**

	nom.	prep.
this	zun	sun

these	zune	sune
that	xune	nun
those	xune	nune

Demonstratives do not have a separate nominalisation. For example, 'I want those' is translated as *feli xa nune*.

10.5 Possessive determiners

The following table shows the possessive determiners. The determiners in the table are arranged by their corresponding pronoun. For example, the pronoun corresponding to *nô* is *na*, which means 'I', so *nô* must mean 'my'. Like articles, possessive determiners do not have separate singular and plural forms. It is the noun that is inflected for plurality. So, for example, we have *nô puk* (my book) and *nô puke* (my books).

corresponding pronoun	possessive determiner (plain)	possessive determiner (nominative)
na	nô	xô
fu	fô	vô
ka	kô	gô
sa	sô	zô
mas	masô	wasô
men	menô	wenô
fo	fai	vai
kê	koi	goi
sê	soi	zoi

The following are the nominalisations of the possessive determiners. For example, *nonso* means 'mine' as in 'it is mine'.

corresponding determiner	possessive nominalisation			
	plain		nominative	
	singular	plural	singular	plural
nô	nonso	nonse	xonso	xonse
fô	fonso	fonse	vonso	vonse
kô	konso	konse	gonso	gonse
sô	sonso	sonse	zonso	zonse
masô	masoi	masoie	wasoi	wasoie
menô	menoi	menoie	wenoi	wenoie

fai	faiso	faise	vaiso	vaise
koi	koiso	koise	goiso	goise
soi	soiso	soise	zoiso	zoise

10.6 Numbers

		non-coda form	subspec.		spec.		superspec.	
			plain	dist.	plain	dist.	plain	dist.
1	plain							
	nom.							
2	plain	tū	tasi		tosu		tese	
	nom.	dō	dasi		dosu		dese	
3	plain	tok	taksi		toksu		tekse	
	nom.	dok	daksi		doksu		dekse	
4	plain	kus	kasti		kustu		kiste	
	nom.	gus	gasti		gostu		geste	
5	plain	pan	pandi		pondu		pende	
	nom.	ban	bandi		bondu		bende	
6	plain	nis	naski		nosku		neske	
	nom.	nis	xaski		xosku		xeske	
7	plain	sem	sampi		sompu		sempe	
	nom.	zem	zampi		zompu		zempe	
8	plain	maif	mafi		mofu		mefe	
	nom.	waif	wafi		wofu		wefe	
9	plain	lek	laksi		loksu		lekse	
	nom.	rek	raksi		roksu		rekse	
10	plain	nai	nasi		nosu		nese	
	nom.	xai	xasi		xosu		xese	
11	plain		nainā		naine		naini	
	nom.		xainā		xaine		xaini	
12	plain	naitū	naitasi		naitosu		naitese	
	nom.	xaitū	xaitasi		xaitosu		xaitese	
20	plain	tūnai	tūnasi		tūnosu		tūnese	
	nom.	dūnai	dūnasi		dūnosu		dūnese	
30	plain	toknai	toknasi		toknosu		toknese	
	nom.	doknai	doknasi		doknosu		doknese	
100	plain	kai	katsi		kotsu		ketse	
	nom.	gai	gatsi		gotsu		getse	
234	plain	tūkai	tūkai		tūkai		tūkai	
		toknai	toknai		toknai		toknai	
		kus	kasti		kustu		kiste	
	nom.	dūkai	dūkai		dūkai		dūkai	

		toknai kus	toknai kasti		toknai kustu		toknai kiste	
1000	plain	tausen	tasni		tosnu		tesne	
	nom.	dausen	dasni		dosnu		desne	
10 ⁶	plain							
	nom.							
10 ⁹	plain							
	nom.							
10 ¹²	plain							
	nom.							

zero

ordinals

ordinal nominalisations

cardinal nominalisations

The cardinal coda forms are each divided into subspecific, specific and superspecific forms. For example:

kefo xa tosu maisen
eat.PST NOM.I two.SP apple.PL
I ate two apples

feli xa tasi maisen
want.PRS NOM.I two apple.PL
I want two apples

feli xa kamē dese wenken
want.PRS NOM.I come.INF NOM.two.SPSP NOM.person.PL
'I want two people to come' (i.e. 'there are two people I want to come')

They are also indefinite by default. The definite form is formed by placing a definite article before the number. For example:

se tosu manen
se two.SP man.PL
the two men

The non-coda forms are used to refer to the numbers without an argument e.g. 'the number two', 'two plus two is four'. They are also used to form compound words e.g. *tōrad* = 'bicycle' (literally 'two-wheel') and 'compound numbers'. For example, the subspecific form of 'two hundred and thirty four', as seen in the

table above, uses non-coda forms for the 'two hundred and thirty' part of the number with only the 'four' being a non-coda form that is declined for specificity.

Ordinal numbers are formed by adding the suffix **xxx** to the non-coda form. For example:

xxx

There are no morphologically distinct nominalisations of numbers. For example, we would say

feli xa tosu maisen
want.PRS NOM.I two.SP apple.PL
I want two apples

and

feli xa tosu
want.PRS NOM.I two.SP
I want two

The same applies to other specificity levels:

feli xa tasi maisen
want.PRS NOM.I two.SPSP apple.PL
I want two apples

and

feli xa tasi
want.PRS NOM.I two.SP
I want two

Numbers are also declined for distributivity. For example, in the sentence 'we can construct clauses with all four of these interpretations', 'four' would be distributive.

10.7 Articles

10.7.1 Definite articles

The definite articles are shown in the table below. The effect of the specificity of the articles has already been explained in section **10.2**.

	plain	nom.
Specific	se	ze
Subspecific	sā	zā
Superspecific	si	zi

10.7.2 Indefinite articles

The indefinite articles are shown in the table below. The effect of the specificity of the articles has already been explained in section 10.2.

	Countable		Uncountable	
	plain	nom.	plain	nom.
Specific	ne	xe	neme	xeme
Subspecific	nā	xā	nāmo	xāmo
Superspecific	ni	xi	nimi	ximi

Note that these articles do not have separate singular and plural forms. Only the noun is inflected for plurality. So, for example, we have

ne mais
an apple

ne maise
some apples

10.8 Quantifiers, their associated adverbs, and coda forms

The quantifiers are a group of determiners derived from certain adverbs, and are the coda forms of those adverbs. Both quantifiers and these associated adverbs are declined for case, specificity, and distributivity.

The table below shows the adverbs.

	plain.		nom.	
	subsp./ sp.	supersp.	subsp./ sp.	supersp.
very	tē	tese	dē	dese
not very	fā	fase	vā	vase
less	lê	lese	rê	rese
more	mô	mose	wô	wose
enough	mabi	maboi	wabi	waboi
completely				
too	tō	tose	dō	dose
so	sō	sose	zō	zose

And this table shows the quantifiers.

adverb	English	case	subspecific		specific		superspecific	
			Plain	Dist.	Plain	Dist.	Plain	Dist.
tē	many, a lot of	plain	tani	tanxi	tono	tonxo	tene	tenxe
		nom.	dani	danxi	dono	donxo	dene	denxe
fā	few, not a lot of	plain	fari	falxi	foru	folxu	ferere	felxe
		nom.	vari	valxi	voro	volxo	vere	velxe
mô	more	plain	mari	malxi	moro	molxo	mere	melxe
		nom.	wari	walxi	woro	wolxo	were	welxe
lê	less, fewer	plain	labi	labxi	lobu	lobxu	lebe	lebxe
		nom.	rabi	rabxi	robu	robxu	rebe	rebxe
	all, every, each, any	plain	-	-	nulu	nulxu	nile	nilxe
		nom.	-	-	xulu	xulxu	xile	xilxe
mabi	enough	plain	mabi	mabxi	mobo	mobxo	mebe	mexbe
		nom.	wabi	wabxi	wobo	wobxo	webe	webxe

Firstly, examples of each adverb being used at different specificity levels will be given. The same will then be done for the quantifiers.

Quantifying adverbs

The specific forms of the adverbs are the simplest and are used in sentences such as

mô fasten kino ga
more.SP fast.ADV go.PST NOM.he
he went faster

tē fasten kino ga
very.SP fast.ADV go.PST NOM.he
he went very fast

As can be seen in the table, there is no distinction between the specific and subspecific forms.

The superspecific forms are used in sentences such as

kato xa mē ga mose fasten kinē
think.PST NOM.I be.INF NOM.he more.SPSP fast.ADV go.INF
I thought he was going faster

Here, the superspecific is used because xXX. Likewise, in the sentence

kato xa mē ga tese fasten kinē
think.PST NOM.I be.INF NOM.he very.SPSP fast.ADV go.INF
I thought he was going very fast

the superspecific is used because XXX.

As another example, consider the sentence

felo ga tose fasten kinē ga
want.PST NOM.he too.SPSP fast.ADV go.INF NOM.he
he wanted him to go too fast

Here, we use the superspecific because although the speed he wanted him to go at was too high, he may not have been aware that it was too high, falsely thinking it was an inappropriate speed. If we use the specific instead, the sentence would mean that he wanted him to go at an inappropriately high speed and was aware that it was inappropriately high. It could be, for example, that he maliciously wanted the other person to injure themselves.

tono etc.

The adverbial form of this quantifier means 'very' (with adjectives) or 'very much' (with verbs). For example:

mi zen tē kom
CONT.PRS NOM.it very big
It is very big

se tē kome fak
se very big.COD house
the very big house

tē magi xa ka
very like.PRS NOM.I he
I like him very much

The determiner form means 'many', 'much', or 'a lot of' and can either describe a countable quantity e.g. 'many people' or 'a lot of people' or an uncountable (but still measurable) quantity e.g. 'a lot of anger', 'a lot of heat'.

We have already compared a sentence with a 'specific many' to a distributed 'superspecific many' in the example below.

neso lenatê zen li nā menk i pālê tonon pālonen
easy learn.PASS.HAB NOM.it by nā person.CNS NOM.o speak.HAB many.SP
language.PL

neso lenatê zen li nā menk i pālê tenxe pālonen
easy learn.PASS.HAB NOM.it by nā person.CNS NOM.o speak.HAB many.SPSP.DIST
language.PL

In the example below, a sentence with a 'subspecific many' is compared to a sentence with a 'specific many'.

feli xa tani puken
want.PRS NOM.I many.SBSP book.PL
I want many books (as opposed to few)

feli xa tonon puken
want.PRS NOM.I many.SP book.PL
There are many books I want

foru etc.

The adverbial form of this quantifier means 'not very' (with adjectives) or 'not very much' (with verbs). For example:

mi zen fā kom
CONT.PRS NOM.it not.very big
It is not very big

se fā kome fak
se not.very big.COD house
the not very big house

fā magi xa ka
not.very like.PRS NOM.I he
I don't like him very much

The determiner form means 'not many', 'few', or 'not much' and can either describe a countable quantity e.g. 'not many people' or 'few people' or an uncountable (but still measurable) quantity e.g. 'not much anger', 'not much heat'.

The examples for *fari* etc. are analogous to the example for *tani* etc. So we have

neso lenatê zen li nā menk i pālê foru pālonen
easy learn.PASS.HAB NOM.it by nā person.CNS NOM.o speak.HAB few.SP language.PL

neso lenatê zen li nā menk i pālê felxe pālonen
easy learn.PASS.HAB NOM.it by nā person.CNS NOM.o speak.HAB few.SPSP.DIST
language.PL

We also have

feli xa fari puken
want.PRS NOM.I few.SBSP book.PL
I want few books (as opposed to many)

feli xa foru puken
want.PRS NOM.I few.SP book.PL
There are few books I want

moro etc.

These are translations of the word 'more'.

Example 1:

feli xa mari puken
want.PRS NOM.I more.SBSP book.PL

The above sentence means 'I want more books' in the sense that 'I want the number of books I have to be greater. I do not have specific books in mind.'

feli xa moro puken
want.PRS NOM.I more.SP book.PL

The above sentence means 'I want more books' in the sense that 'there are specific books that I want to add to the books that I already have.'

Example 2:

feli xa mā kamē woro wenken
want.PRS NOM.I mā come.INF NOM.more.SP NOM.person.PL

The above sentence means 'I want more people to come' in the sense that 'I want the number of people who come to be greater. I do not have specific people in mind.'

feli xa mā kamē were wenken
want.PRS NOM.I mā come.INF NOM.more.SPSP NOM.person.PL

The above sentence means 'I want more people to come' in the sense that 'there are more people that I want to come'.

There is also an adverbial form, *mô*. For example:

mi zen mô kom
CONT.PRS NOM.it more big
It is bigger

se mô kome fak
se more big.COD house
the bigger house

lobu etc.
These are translations of the word 'less'.

Example 1:

feli xa lobo puken sū ka
want.PRS NOM.I less.SP book.PL than he

The above sentence means 'I want fewer books than him' in the sense that 'the number of books I want is less than the number of books he wants'.

feli xa labi puken
want.PRS NOM.I less.SBSP book.PL

The above sentence means 'I want fewer books' in the sense that 'I want the number of books I have to be less, but I do not have specific books in mind that I want to get rid of'.

Example 2:

feli xa mā kamē robo wenken
want.PRS NOM.I mā come.INF NOM.less.SP NOM.person.PL

The above sentence means 'I want fewer people to come' in the sense that 'I want the number of people who come to be less'.

feli xa mā kamē rebe wenken sū feli ga

want.PRS NOM.I mā come.INF NOM.less.SPSP NOM.person.PL than want.PRS NOM.he

The above sentence means 'I want fewer people to come than him' in the sense that 'the number of people I want to come is less than the number of people he wants to come'.

There is also an adverbial form, *lê*. For example:

mi zen lê naf

CONT.PRS NOM.it less red

It is less red

se lê nafe fak

se less red-COD house

the less red house

nulu etc

nulu is the word for 'all' or 'every'. For example, *feli xa nulu puke* means 'I want all books' or 'I want every book'. Unlike the other determiners, there is no subspecific form, however there is an adverbial form, *nel*, which means 'completely' or 'totally'.

The superspecific, *nile*, form can often be translated as 'any'.

Example 1:

kani vu fālē nulu kād

can.PRS NOM.you choose.INF all.SP card

You can pick every card/ You can pick all cards

kani vu fālē nile kād

can.PRS NOM.you choose.INF all.SPSP card

You can pick any card

Example 2:

neso lenatê zen li nā menk i pālē nulu pālonen

easy learn.PASS.HAB NOM.it li nā person.CNS NOM.o speak.INF all.SP language.PL

The above means 'it is easily learned by people who speak every language' in the sense that 'if a person speaks every language, it is easily for him to learn'.

neso lenatê zen li nā menk i pālē ne nile pālonen

easy learn.PASS.HAB NOM.it li nā person.CNS NOM.o speak.INF ne all.SPSP language.PL

The above means 'it is easily learned by a person who speaks any language' i.e. that it is easy to learn no matter what language you speak.

The English word 'any' would not always be translated as *nile*. As already explained in other sections, in many situations where English would use 'any' an indefinite article is used in *kōxō*.

~~XXX~~

These are translations of some, as in 'I want some water' but not as in 'I want some books'. In other words, it is the translation of the uncountable 'some'.

Example 1:

mabi etc

These are translations of the word 'enough'.

Example 1:

feli xa mabi koif

want.PRS NOM.I enough.SBSP food

The above means 'I want enough food' in the sense that 'I want to have enough food, rather than not enough food'.

feli xa mobo koif

want.PRS NOM.I enough.SP food

The above means 'I want enough food' in the sense that 'it would excessive to want more than what I already what'.

Example 2:

feli xa mā kamē wobo wenken

want.PRS NOM.I mā come.INF NOM.enough.SP NOM.person.PL

The above means 'I want enough people to come' in the sense that 'I want the number of people that come to be enough, rather than insufficient'.

feli xa mā kamē webe wenken
want.PRS NOM.I mā come.INF NOM.enough.SPSP NOM.person.PL

The above means 'I want enough people to come' in the sense that 'it would be excessive to want more people to come than what I already want'.

There is also a verbal or adverbial form, *mabi*. For example:

mi zen mabi kom
CONT.PRS NOM.it enough big
It is big enough

se mabi kome fak
se enough big.COD house
the big enough house

mi zen mabi
CONT.PRS NOM.it enough
It is enough/ It is sufficient

Notes on the translations of 'most' and 'least'

The adverbs *mô* (more), *lê* (less), *tē* (very) and *fā* (not very) also function as determiners, as described earlier in this section, each with specific and superspecific forms. Since in English, 'most' functions as both an adverb and a determiner, one might ask whether the adverbs *nê* (most) and *len* (least) can function as determiners, each with specific and superspecific forms. The answer is no. The translation of the English determiner 'most' is *ne maue* (literally 'a majority'). For example:

feli xa nā maue se puken
want.PRS NOM.I nā majority se book.PL
I want most of the books (as opposed to not as many)

feli xa ne maue se puken
want.PRS NOM.I ne majority se book.PL
I want most of the books (I have specific ones in mind)

feli xa nā maue puken

want.PRS NOM.I nā majority book.PL
I want most books (as opposed to not many)

feli xa ne maue puken
want.PRS NOM.I ne majority book.PL
I want most books (I have specific ones in mind)

feli xa sā maue se puken
want.PRS NOM.I sā majority se book.PL
I want the most books (I want my share to be the largest)

feli xa se maue se puken
want.PRS NOM.I se majority se book.PL
I want the most books (I want certain books, which are more in number than the amount anyone else wants)

'Least' is not used as a determiner in English anyway. We might say 'I want most books', but we would not say 'I want least books'. However, the opposite of *ne maue* (a majority) is *ne moie* (a minority). Its use follows the same pattern. For example:

feli xa nā moie se puken
want.PRS NOM.I nā minority se book.PL
I want a minority of the books (as opposed to most of them)

feli xa ne moie se puken
want.PRS NOM.I ne minority se book.PL
I want a minority of the books (there are some books I want, which are a minority of the total)

feli xa sā moie se puken
want.PRS NOM.I sā minority se book.PL
I want the least books (I want my share to be the smallest)

feli xa se moie se puken
want.PRS NOM.I se minority se book.PL
I want the least books (I want certain books, which are lesser in number than the amount anyone else wants)

10.8.1 An alternative to the distributive in quantifiers

Examples were given earlier of the distributivity and specificity being used simultaneously in quantifiers. As a reminder, one of these examples was

neso lenatê zen li nā menk i pālê tenxe pālonen
easy learn.PASS.HAB NOM.it by nā person.CNS NOM.o speak.HAB many.SPSP.DIST
language.PL

This sentence can be rewritten as

neso lenatê zen li nā menk i pālê neno ev tene pālonen
easy learn.PASS.HAB NOM.it by nā person.CNS NOM.o speak.HAB ne.NZ of
many.SPSP language.PL

Here, *tenxe pālonen* (many languages) has been replaced with *nenō ev tene pālonen* (one of many languages). It is worth noting the equivalence of these two, although as a matter of style we would always use the distributive because it is faster and preserves the grammatical structure of other sentences, in much the same way as using the superspecific instead of *ha* preserves grammatical structure.

10.8.2 *pō-, tō-, kū-, kasai*

Certain determiners and adverbs can be modified using the prefixes *pō-*, *tō-*, *kū-* and *kasai*, as shown in the following table.

With verbs, these prefixes are used alone (bearing in mind that there is no distinction in *kōxō* between verbs and adjectives). This differs slightly from English in that 'so', 'too', and 'how' can be used alone with adjectives (e.g. 'it is so big') but not usually with verbs (we would normally say 'I like him so much' rather than 'I like him so', which sounds slightly archaic). So in *kōxō*, we have

mi zen pō naf
CONT.PRS NOM.it so red
It is so red

pō magi xa ka
so like.PRS NOM.I he
I like him so much

but would not say something like *pō tē magi xa ka*, although this is closer to how it would be said in English, and certainly not something like *mi zen pō tē naf*.

	<i>pō-</i>	<i>tō-</i>	<i>kū-</i>	<i>kasai</i>
-	<i>pō</i> = 'so' / 'so	<i>tō</i> = 'too' / 'too	<i>kū</i> = 'how' / 'how	<i>kasai</i> = 'how' /

	much' (with verb)	much' (with verb)	much' (with verb)	'how much' (with verb)
<i>tono</i> (determiner form of <i>tē</i>)	<i>pōtono</i> = 'so many'/ 'so much' (with noun)	<i>tōtono</i> = 'too many'/ 'too much' (with noun)	<i>kūtono</i> = 'how many'/ 'how much' (with noun)	<i>kasai tono</i> = 'how many'/ 'how much' (with noun)
<i>fā</i>	<i>pōfā</i> = (difficult to translate for adjective)/ 'so little' (with verb)	<i>tōfā</i> = (difficult to translate for adjective)/ 'too little' (with verb)	<i>kūfā</i> = (difficult to translate for adjective)/ 'how little' (with verb)	<i>kasai fā</i> = (difficult to translate for adjective)/ 'how little' (with verb)
<i>foru</i> (determiner form of <i>fā</i>)	<i>pōforu</i> = 'so few'/ 'so little' (with noun)	<i>tōforu</i> = 'too few'/ 'too little' (with noun)	<i>kūforu</i> = 'how few'/ 'how little' (with noun)	<i>kasai foru</i> = 'how few'/ 'how little' (with noun)
<i>mô</i>	<i>pōmô</i> = 'so much more' (with adjective or verb)	<i>tōmô</i> = 'too much more' (with adjective or verb)	<i>kūmô</i> = 'how much more' (with adjective or verb)	<i>kasai mô</i> = 'how much more' (with adjective or verb)
<i>moro</i> (determiner form of <i>mô</i>)	<i>pōmoro</i> = 'so many more'/ 'so much more' (with noun)	<i>tōmoro</i> = 'too many more'/ 'too much more' (with noun)	<i>kūmoro</i> = 'how many more'/ 'how much more' (with noun)	<i>kasai moro</i> = 'how many more'/ 'how much more' (with noun)
<i>lê</i>	<i>pōlê</i> = 'so much less' (with adjective or verb)	<i>tōlê</i> = 'too much less' (with adjective or verb)	<i>kūlê</i> = 'how much less' (with adjective or verb)	<i>kasai lê</i> = 'how much less' (with adjective or verb)
<i>lobo</i> (determiner form of <i>lê</i>)	<i>pōlobo</i> = 'so fewer'/ 'so much less' (with noun)	<i>tōlobo</i> = 'too fewer'/ 'too much less' (with noun)	<i>kūlobo</i> = 'how fewer'/ 'how much less' (with noun)	<i>kasai lobo</i> = 'how fewer'/ 'how much less' (with noun)

Each of these four prefixes (except *kasai*) has a nominative and prepositional form, as shown below:

Nom.	Prep.
pō	bō
tō	dō
kū	gū
kasai	-

Note that the difference between *kū-* and *kasai* is that *kasai* is used to ask questions. For example, *kū* means 'how' or 'how much' as in 'I was shocked by how big it was'. *kasai* would be the corresponding interrogative form, used to ask questions. For example:

mi zen kasai kom?
 CONT.PRS NOM.it how.much big?
 How big is it?

kasai magi vu sen?
 how.much like.PRS NOM.you it?
 How much do you like it?

Note that quantitative nominalisations such as 'size', 'temperature' etc. are translated using *kū* and *kasai*. For example:

se kūkom
 se how.much-big
 the size

se kūmoz
 se how.much-hot
 the temperature

se kūfast
 se how.much-fast
 the speed

The prefixes in the table can be used with all forms of each determiner. For example, with *tene* as well as *tono*. For example, *pōtene* means 'so many'. *tē* and *tono* and its variations and *fā* and *foru* and its variations can be used with *sē* to form various expressions. For example:

kefasi xa pōtono koif sē kanos
eat.FUT NOM.I so-many.SP food sē possible
I will eat as much food as possible

kefasi xa pōporo koif sē kanos
eat.FUT NOM.I so-few.SP food sē possible
I will eat as little food as possible

pō sē kanos sairasi xa
pō sē possible travel.FUT NOM.I
I will travel as much as possible

pō fā sē kanos sairasi xa
pō fā sē possible travel.FUT NOM.I
I will travel as little as possible

mô, *moru lê*, and *lobu* and their variations can each be combined with *tē* in the following ways:

tē moro
many more, a lot more (with nouns)

tē mô
much more, a lot more (with verbs or adjectives)

tē lobo
much less, a lot less (with nouns)

tē lê
much less, a lot less (with verbs or adjectives)

10.9 Chains of determiners

Chains of determiners can be used in much the same way they are in English. For example, *magi xa nulu se menken* ('I like all the people') contains the determiner chain *nulu se* (all the). Note that the word 'whole' or 'entire' is translated like this. For example, *nulu se fak* = 'the whole house'. Unlike in English chains, which often contain the word 'of', *kōxō* chains never contain an equivalent of 'of'. For example, 'some of the' is translated as *nenoi se* (literally 'some the').

10.10 The premarker *komes*

The pre-marker *komes* is only used in rare circumstances. Its function is to make what is marked literal rather than a placeholder for something else. (According to the non-substitution principle, nothing should be a placeholder, but it has proven necessary to make certain exceptions to this principle). For example:

mi wot komes sen?

be.PRS NOM.what komes it?

'What is 'it'?' (i.e. what does the word 'it' actually mean?)

10.11 Nominalisations of determiners

Quantifiers and numbers do not have distinct nominalisations. Possessive determiners, demonstratives, and articles do. The nominalisation of possessive determiners and demonstratives has already been covered. The table below shows the nominalisations of articles.

Article	Singular nominalisation	Uncountable nominalisation	Plural nominalisation
nā	nāno	nāmo	nānoi
ne	nenō	nemo	nenoi
ni	nino	nimo	ninoi
se	sa		sê

These nominalisations are used in situations such as:

feli xa nāno

want.PRS NOM.I nāno

I want one

feli xa nānoi

want.PRS NOM.I nānoi

I want some

On the other hand, quantifiers do not have distinct nominalisations. Hence we have

tani maisen

many.SBSP apple.PL

many apples

feli xa tani

want.PRS NOM.I many.SBSP

I want many

The nominalisations of the specific definite article *se* are *sen* (it) and *sê* (they inanimate). There are no nominalisations for the definite article at other levels of specificity. *sen* and *sê* are hence sometimes used in situations where we would use those 'that' or 'those' in English rather than 'it' or 'they'. For example:

mi vô denkone sê ev nã kude menek

be.PRS NOM.his NOM.think-on-PL sê of nã good.COD person

his thoughts are those of a good person

sen, *sê*, *ka*, and *kê* can be used to form free relative clauses, as already explained in section 8.

11. Verb conjugation

11.1 Introduction to verbs

The verb *ondakē* (to accept) is conjugated below as an example of verb conjugation.

	null	present	past
simple	ondakē	ondaki	ondako
habitual	-	ondakê	-
perfect	ondakarē	ondakari	ondakaro
futural	ondakasē	ondakasi	ondakaso
futural perfect	ondakarasē	ondakarasi	ondakaraso
IMPERATIVE	ondaku		
PROPOSITIVE	ondakausi		
GERUND	ondakan		
PASSIVE PARTICIPLE	ondakad		
ADJECTIVAL	ondake		
PASSIVE ADJECTIVAL	ondakade		

It is worth pointing out that the null futural and past futural are rarely used, with the present futural simply being the future tense and hence being much more common. The past and present futural perfect are even rarer.

11.2 Auxiliary verbs

Aspect is expressed using auxiliary verbs. These are:

continuous	mē
progressive	andē
habitual	nē

Each of these can be conjugated. For example:

	null	present	past
simple	mē	mi	mo
perfect	marē	mari	maro
futural	masē	masi	maso
futural perfect	marasē	marasi	maraso
IMPERATIVE	mu		
PROPOSITIVE	mausi		
GERUND	men		

Examples of auxiliary verbs being used include:

mi xa mirē ka
CONT.PRES NOM.*I look*.INF *he*
I am looking at him

mi xa tē fasten kinē
CONT.PRS NOM.*I very fast*.ADV *go*.INF
I am going very quickly

11.3 Case marking on verbs

Like nouns, verbs can also be declined for case.

The nominative

As has already been explained, when a verb phrase is in the nominative, the initial consonants of the verb and any adverbs are all mutated. For example:

mi dō rende ginē kek
be.PRS NOM.*too* NOM.*slow*-COD NOM.*go*.INF *bad*
going too slowly is bad

An alternative to this is

mi zen kek dō rende ginē
CONT.PRS NOM.*it bad* NOM.*too* NOM.*slow*-COD NOM.*go*.INF
It is bad to go too slowly

Unmarked

In *kōxō*, the accusative is not marked, however we can think of verbs as being in the accusative in certain situations. For example, in the sentence

feli xa kinē
want.PRS NOM.*I go*.INF
I want to go

kinē is essentially in the accusative since it is the object of *feli*. Note that the verb *kinē* is not conjugated for tense i.e. it is in the 'null tense'. This is similar to the English structure, where in sentences such as 'I want to go', 'to go' is in the infinitive. Because *kinē* is without tense, we assume the tense is 'aligned' with *feli* i.e. that the sentence means 'I want to go now' even though *kinē* is not explicitly in the present tense. We will come back to this idea of alignment in the next section.

Similarly, a verb with an adverb can be in the accusative. For example, in the sentence

feli xa lenden kinē
want.PRS NOM.I slow.ADV go.INF
I want to go slowly

lenden kinē is in the accusative. And of course, a verb can be explicitly marked by *mā*, which is closely related to the accusative case.

Another grammatical function of verbs that is unmarked is being the predicate of an auxiliary verb. We saw examples of this in the previous section, such as

mi xa mirē ka
CONT.PRES NOM.I look.INF he
I am looking at him

11.4 The null tense

A verb is said to be in the null tense when it has not been conjugated for tense. For example, *kinē* (to go) is in the null tense, *kini* and *kino* are in the present and past tense.

The null tense is used to align tenses. For example, in the sentence

kato xa mā kinē ga
think.PST NOM.I mā go.INF NOM.he
I thought he was going

kato is in the past tense and *kinē* is in the null tense. Because *kinē* is in the null tense, we assume that the 'going' is taking place at the same time as the 'thinking'. Compare this to English, where both verbs are in the past tense. From a more objective perspective, the English construction is quite strange. It seems to suggest that the 'going' is in the past relative to the 'thinking', meaning something more like 'I thought he had been going', although as English speakers we know that this is not the case.

11.5 Aspect

11.5.1 Introduction to aspect

There are five basic aspects in *kōxō*: perfective, continuous, progressive, perfect, and habitual. There are also two compound aspects - the perfect continuous and perfect progressive.

Every verb has a default aspect which is either the continuous or perfective. When a verb is in its default aspect, there is no need for an auxiliary verb to show aspect. For example, *ondakē* (accept) has perfective default aspect, so *ondako* and *ondaki* are automatically perfective, but we must use auxiliary verbs to form the continuous forms e.g. *mo ondakē* and *mi ondakē*. Perfective verbs are not normally used in their default aspect in the present tense. An exception to this is that they may be used when telling a story in the present tense.

On the other hand, *tenē* (have) has continuous default aspect. So *teno* and *tai* are continuous. This is similar to the situation in English, where we would say 'I have' and 'I had', but usually not 'I am having' and 'I was having', despite forming the continuous using 'to be' with many other verbs. The verbs that have continuous default aspect in *kōxō* are the same as the ones that have it in English. Examples include *tenē* (to have), *magē* (to like), *lovē* (to love), *kosē* (to enjoy), *felē* (to want), *fisē* (to see), *kenē* (to know), *fulē* (to feel), and others.

11.5.2 The continuous aspect

The continuous aspect is used in two ways.

i) to indicate a constant state that does not inherently have to come to an end. For example: 'I am happy', 'I am sitting', 'I accept'.

ii) to indicate an action that does not inherently have to come to an end e.g. 'I am talking', 'I am walking', 'I am breathing'.

When the continuous aspect is not default, it is expressed with auxiliary verbs. For example:

mi xa mirē sen
CONT.PRS NOM.I look.INF it
I am looking at it

mō xa mirē sen
CONT.PST NOM.I look.INF it
I was looking at it

Unlike in English, a distinction is made between the continuous and progressive aspects.

11.5.3 The progressive aspect

The progressive is used for actions that must inherently come to an end. For example, 'I am eating the apple' (once the apple is eaten, the action ends), 'I am raising the temperature by five degrees' (once the temperature is raised, the action has been completed. However, the sentence 'I am raising the temperature' could be used with the continuous if you mean you are continually raising the temperature with no fixed goal in mind), 'I am cancelling my subscription' (once the subscription is cancelled, the action is complete), 'I am searching for him' (once he is found the action is complete) etc.

The difference between the continuous and progressive can be seen with the verb *ondakē* (accept), which can use both aspects. *po xa ondakē* means 'I was (in the process of) accepting', *mo xa ondakē* means 'I accepted' (i.e. was in a state of acceptance, not did the action of accepting).

11.5.4 The habitual aspect

The habitual is used to express actions done on a regular basis or that are generally true, not just at the present time. For example:

'I go to school'
'I play football'

In English, the present habitual is conflated with the present perfective. We can say 'I was riding my bike' or 'I rode my bike' and we know that both of these actions are in the past, but with the present tense versions of these statements – 'I am riding my bike' and 'I ride my bike' – only the first statement is interpreted as being in the present and the second is interpreted as the habitual. Since some *kōxō* verbs in the present tense are in the continuous aspect by default, this would have the potential to confuse English speakers, since a *kōxō* sentence such as

nezi xa mis
need.PRS NOM.I water
I need water

may seem like it is in the habitual to an English speaker (I need water on a regular basis), when it is in fact in the present continuous (I need water now). However, this confusion is avoided by the existence of a present habitual suffix that is distinct from the present indicative suffix. So, the present habitual version of the previous example would be

nezê xa mis

There is also a past habitual, expressed using an auxiliary verb

no xa lidē nō torad
HAB.PST NOM.I ride.INF my bike
I used to ride my bike

And a null habitual

feli xa nē lidē nō torad
want.PRS NOM.I HAB ride.INF my bike
I want to start riding my bike (on a regular basis)

11.5.5 The perfective aspect

The perfective is used to indicate that an action occurs fully, rather than being in the process of occurring or continually occurring. For example, *tako xa* means 'I took' (not 'I was taking'), *kino xa* means 'I went' (not 'I was going'). Verbs that are continuous by default must be **modified by the prefix *тино-*** to put them in the perfective aspect. This is something that rarely needs to be done. **For example, 'accept' is continuous by default in the present tense, so we would say**

тинондәки xa sen
PFV-accept.PRS NOM.I it
I hereby accept it

11.5.6 The perfect aspect

The perfect is formed using a suffix and can be combined with the past, present, future, or null tense. For example:

kefari xa sen
eat.PRF.PRS NOM.I it
I have eaten it

kefaro xa sen
eat.PRF.PST NOM.I it
I had eaten it

kefarasi xa sen
eat.PRF.FUT NOM.I it
I will have eaten it

kato xa mā kefarē xa sen
think.PST NOM.I mā eat.PRF.INF NOM.I it

I thought I had eaten it

The last example is an interesting application of the perfect in which the past is embedded into the past and deserves to be discussed more fully. Consider the sentence 'I thought you were writing'. In English, the event of writing is in the present relative to the event of thinking, but is written using the past tense because both the thinking and the writing are in the past relative to the speaker speaking the sentence. In kōxō, 'writing' would be translated using the null tense which by default means it happens simultaneously with the 'thinking' that it is embedded into. So, the kōxō sentence is:

kato xa mā mē vu kakē
think.PST NOM.I mā CONT NOM.you write.INF
I thought you were writing

If the 'writing' is in the past relative to the 'thinking', there are several possibilities, all involving the perfect. These are summarised in the table below, along with the above example and the translation of 'I was writing when you called' for comparison:

KŌXŌ	ENGLISH	RELATIONS
<i>mē xa kakē fon kalo vu</i>	I was writing when you called	'writing' simultaneous with 'calling'
<i>kato xa mā <u>mē vu kakē</u></i>	I thought you were writing	'writing' simultaneous with 'thinking'
<i>konto ga nem mā [fon kalarē winna <u>mē xa kakē</u>]</i>	He told me [he was writing when I called]	'writing' at a specified point in the past relative to telling
<i>konto ga nem mā [fon kalarē winna <u>marē xa kakē</u>]</i>		'writing' at an unspecified point in the past relative to 'calling'
<i>konto ga nem mā [<u>marē xa kakē</u>]</i>	He told me he had been writing	'writing' at an unspecified point in the past relative to 'telling'

Notes

Square brackets have been used so that the examples are not further complicated by bracketing ambiguities, which is one of the few ambiguities that are still present in kōxō.

In the third example, the writing takes place before the call. I have avoided translating it due to ambiguity. It could be translated as 'He told me that when I

called he had been writing' or, but this could be misinterpreted so that the call and writing are simultaneous. A better translation is 'He told me that [he had been writing at some point before I called]'.

The equivalent of the English perfect continuous (e.g. 'have been', 'had been') is formed similarly as in English, with the auxiliary verb *mē* being conjugated into the perfect. For example:

mari xa fādē
CONT.PRF.PRS NOM.I wait.INF
I have been waiting

11.5.7 The futural aspect

The futural present is simply the future tense. For example

parasi xa sen
do.FUT NOM.I it
I will do it

The futural is also used for embedding the future into the past or future in the same sense that the perfect is used for embedding the past into the past or future. The 'future in past' also exists in English, although it is often ignored in works on English grammar since it uses 'would' and is therefore conflated with the conditional. For example, 'I thought he would always be here', 'I thought everything would turn out well'.

kato xa mā kamasē ga
think.PST NOM.I mā come.FL NOM.he
I thought he would come

tando xa se mols i taraso mā nō mased
meet.PST NOM.I se woman.CNS NOM.o become.FL mā my wife
I met the woman who would become my wife

Note that the term 'future in past' is somewhat vague as it encompasses moments after a past time but before the present, the present, and times after the present. However, the 'future in past' formed with *-aso* is best used only for the first of these cases. If we return to the second example, we can see that we could easily use the present tense to form the sentence 'I met the woman who is (now) my wife' or the future tense to form the sentence 'I met the woman who will be my wife (but is not yet)', so we do not need *-aso* for these situations.

The futural is also used in situations such as

kiu kinaso ga
not.ADV go.FL.PST NOM.he
He wouldn't go

kiu letaso ga pare xa sen
not.ADV let.FL.PST NOM.he do.INF NOM.I it
She wouldn't let me do it

The futural can be combined with *mē* to form the equivalent of 'is going to' or 'was going to' i.e. a futural where something is set to happen but could be prevented. For example:

mo xa kamasē
CONT.PST NOM.I come.FL.INF
I was going to come

mi xa kamasē
CONT.PRS NOM.I come.FL.INF
I am going to come

11.5.8 The futural perfect

The present futural perfect is equivalent to the English 'will have'. The other forms are very rarely used. For example:

kato xa mā pararasē xa sen pô nau
think.PST NOM.I do.PRF.FL.INF NOM.I it by now
I thought I would have done it by now

fiso xa se man i pararaso sen pô esenkinē xa
see.PST NOM.I se man i do.PRF.FL.PST it by leave.INF NOM.I
I saw the man who would have done it by the time I left

11.6 The imperative and propositive moods

Kōxō has an imperative and propositive. The imperative, indicated by the suffix -*u*, is addressed to 'you' or 'you plural'. For example:

kinu = Go!
kiu kinu = Don't go!
lende kinu = Go slowly!

The propositive is equivalent to the English 'let's'. For example:

kinausi = Let's go

11.7 The passive voice

The passive is formed with the passive participle and either the auxiliary verb *mē*, which forms the 'passive of being', or *tarē*, which forms the 'passive of becoming'. In particular, the present continuous passive and present perfective passive are always distinct in *kōxō* although this is not the case in English. For example:

fon tarē ze rigen kaiseknamad
when become.INF NOM.se NOM.wire disconnect.PASS
when the wire is (gets) disconnected

fon mē ze rigen kaiseken
when CONT NOM.se NOM.wire disconnect
when the wire is (has been) disconnected

Some more examples of the passive with different aspects:

mo xa ondakad
CONT.PST NOM.I accept.PASS
I was accepted (as in 'throughout the entire year, I was accepted')

taro xa ondakad
become.PST NOM.I accept.PASS
I was accepted/ I got accepted (as in 'by signing the contract, I was accepted')

ando xa tarē ondakad
PROG.PST NOM.I become.INF accept.PASS
I was being accepted

11.8 Complex pronouns

In some situations, exactly who a pronoun refers to may be difficult to recognise. For example, does the sentence

pendo xa kem mō vu parē mot
ask.PST NOM.I he.DAT CONT.PST NOM.you do.INF what

mean 'I asked him what you were doing' or 'I asked him 'What are you doing?' (i.e. 'I asked him what he was doing')? In fact, it means the latter. This is because

the pronoun in the speech or thoughts of the subject must be from the perspective of the subject at the time the action is carried out. We call this the 'quotative principle'. So, in the sentence *pendo xa kem mo vu parē mot* ('I asked him what you were doing'), 'you' is interpreted to be who the subject would call 'you' when he asked the question, which would of course be the person the question was addressed to. To say 'I asked him what you were doing', we would say

ha fu pendo xa kem mo ga parē mot
ha you ask.PST NOM.I he.DAT CONT.PST NOM.he do.INF what

We can change this so that the sentence has the same structure as the original example using the prefix *la*. So the above sentence becomes

pendo xa kem mo rafu parē mot

Since this is nothing but a scope ambiguity, you may be wondering why we have used a new prefix *la* instead of the specificity prefix *min*. The reason is that *min* can be used with possessive determiners in sentences such as

kato xa mā mē vu minnô foseb
think.PST NOM.I mā be.INF NOM.you min-my NOM.friend
I thought you were my friend (a specific person who I know)

In the above example, the purpose of *min* is not to form a complex pronoun or complex possessive determiner, and using it for the above purposes as well as forming complex pronouns could lead to ambiguity. Hence we may have sentences in which *min* and *la* are used together without confusion, such as:

kato ga mā mē rafu minlanô foseb
think.PST NOM.he mā be.INF NOM.la-you min-la-my friend
He thought you were my friend

11.9 The gerund

The gerund of a verb or adjective is formed using the suffix *-an*. This is the most general nominalisation of a verb and is reserved for when the other nominalisations (*-ai*, *-on*, *-im*, *-us*) are not appropriate. For example:

fisan
see.NZ

sight i.e the act or ability to see, as opposed to 'a beautiful sight', which is translated as *miron*.

felan

want.NZ

desire i.e. the feeling or act of desire, as opposed to desire as in 'my desire is to...', which is translated as *felon*.

sokan

search.NZ

search i.e. the event of searching

fugnan

grow.NZ

growth

tefan

lose.NZ

loss

pıskan

bite.NZ

bite

maupoktan

explode.NZ

explosion

fālan

choose.NZ

choice i.e. the full set of options as in 'I had a choice of three items' or act of choosing, as opposed to 'choice' as in 'his choice was the second item', which is translated as *fālim*.

kafnan

argue.NZ

argument i.e. the event of arguing, as opposed to 'argument' as in 'his argument is that...', which is translated as *kafnim*.

Note that though the gerund and present participle are indistinguishable in English, this is not the case in *kōxō*.

11.10 Valency markers

Some verbs can take different sets of case markers and it is sometimes necessary, when the verb does not take any arguments, to indicate which case markers it is taking. In particular, we must sometimes indicate whether a verb is transitive or intransitive. The following table gives a list of prefixes that indicate a verb's valency and, in each case, which set of case markers the prefix indicates that it is taking:

Valency marker		Cases
nom.	prep.	
wal	mal	(<i>nom</i>)
wil	mil	(<i>wā</i>)
xal	nal	(<i>nom, acc</i>)
xil	nil	(<i>nom, mā</i>)

They can be used with coda forms. For example:

milpoltade sairaxo

mil-plan.PASS.COD travel.NZ

planned journey (a journey that has been planned to take place)

malpoltade sairaxo

mal-plan.PASS.COD travel.NZ

planned journey (a journey that has been planned out/ a journey whose itinerary has been planned in detail)

They can also be used to contract phrases. For example, the following two phrases are equivalent.

mi boltē mā nevoj kud

CONT.PRS NOM.plan.INF mā SP.something good

It's good to plan things

mi xilpoltē kud

CONT.PRS NOM.nil-plan.INF good

It's good to plan

Similarly, the following two phrases are also equivalent.

mi boltē nevoj kud

CONT.PRS NOM.plan.INF SP.something good

It's good to plan things out

mi xalpoltē kud
 CONT.PRS NOM.nal-plan.INF good
It's good to plan out

11.11 Second-order verbs

Second-order verbs are verbs that can take another verb as an argument. they include the modal verbs. Some of the most important are shown in the table below.

kōxō	English	Coda form
MODAL VERBS		
mostē	must (deontic)	adjectival
solē	should (deontic)	adjectival
kūvē	can (deontic)	adjectival
kanē	can (epistemic)	adjectival
fodē	<i>conditional</i>	adjectival
OTHER SECOND-ORDER VERBS		
	start	adjectival
	stop	adjectival
mekē	<i>causative</i>	adjectival
tarē	become	adjectival
	keep (continue to do)	adjectival
	keep (do repeatedly)	adjectival
	keep (keep fresh)	

These verbs function in exactly the same way syntactically as every other verb. For example:

mosto xa parē sen
must.PST NOM.I do.INF it
I had to do it

kani xa parē sen
can.PRS NOM.I do.INF it
I can do it

The modal verbs are closely related semantically to modal adverbs. Indeed, 'must' and 'should' each have two translations in kōxō. One translation of each - the deontic form - is in the table above. The others - the epistemic forms - are pre-auxiliary adverbs and are described in [section 12.2.2](#).

Modal verbs in kōxō differ from their English equivalents in that they conjugate normally. For example, we use the past tense of the verb *solē* rather than saying 'should have'. In particular, 'can' in English is highly degenerate, but is conjugable in kōxō. For example, in English we would say 'I want to be able to do it', but in kōxō we can say *feli xa kanē sen* (literally 'I want to can do it'). However, modal verbs do lack some aspects compared to other verbs. For example, *mostē* lacks the futural perfect, and *fodē* lacks the futural, perfect, and futural perfect.

specificity and modal verbs - *mosti xi wenek pare sen etc.*

11.11.1 Notes on second-order verbs

mostē, solē

The epistemic 'must' and 'should' are pre-auxiliary adverbs and were discussed earlier. The deontic 'must' and 'should' are verbs. They each have a coda form. **xxx** translates as 'obligatory' or 'compulsory'. **xxx** translates as 'appropriate'.

kanē, kuvē

Both the epistemic and deontic 'can' are verbs. Examples:

kani xa parē sen

can.PRS NOM. I do. INF it

means 'I can do that' (i.e. I am able to do that).

kuvi xa parē sen

can.PRS NOM. I do. INF it

means 'I can do that' (i.e. I may do that/ I am allowed to do that). *kanē* can be used as a first order verb to mean 'possible'. *kuvē* can be used as a first order verb to mean 'allowed', 'permitted' or 'valid'.

fodē

fodē is the conditional modal verb. In other words, it is the translation of 'would'. For example:

foi xa magē sen

would.PRS NOM. I like. INF it

I would like it

fodo xa mirē ka

would.PST NOM. I watch. INF he

I would have watched him

fodo xa mē mirē ka
would.PST NOM.I CONT.PST watch.INF he
I would have been watching him

Unlike in English, *fodē* is not used with *lē* or *lō*. For example, the sentence 'if I wanted to go, I would go' would be translated as

lō feli xa kinē, kini xa
lō want.PRS NOM.I go.INF, go.PRS NOM.I

So, the 'would' is dropped.

Instead, *fodē* is used in sentences where the 'if' clause is merely implicit. For example, 'I would enjoy doing that' is translated as

foi xa kosē parē sen
would.PRS NOM.I enjoy.INF do.INF it

because the presumed 'if' clause ('if I were doing it') is not actually stated. *fodē* can be used without the accusative. For example, if someone asks *foi vu magē sen?* (Would you like it?), you can reply *foi xa* (I would).

she wouldn't let me vs. she wouldn't have let me, he wouldn't do it vs. he wouldn't have done it etc.

should the conditional always be used with *le/lo* - example: *kato xa ma le kefare ga sen kiu fodare ga kame va* OR *kato xa ma le kefare ga sen kiu kamare ga*

future and null conditional, especially with *le*

mekē
mekē is the causative auxiliary verb. There is also a causative verb suffix *-amē* (see section 14.4). *mekē* can be used with any aspect. For example:

mi gravity mekē mā orbit ze planets mori se sol
CONT.PRS NOM.gravity make.INF mā orbit NOM.se NOM.planet.PL around se sun
gravity makes the planets orbit the sun

mekê wozan mā meltē gel
make.HAB NOM.hot.NZ mā melt.INF NOM.ice
heat makes ice melt

andi xa mekē mā meltē ze gel
PROG.PRS NOM.I make.INF mā melt.INF NOM.se NOM.ice
I'm making the ice melt

tarē

tarē means 'to become'. There is also a verbal prefix meaning 'to become' (see section 14.4). It can be used with adjectival phrases. For example:

taro xa tē sobek
become.PST NOM.I very tired
I got very tired

or with noun phrases. For example:

taro xa mā se sūf
become.PST NOM.I mā se king
I became the king

It can be used with any aspect. For example:

andi xa tarē mô kud
PROG.PRS NOM.I become.INF more good
I'm getting better (and when I have reached a certain standard I will stop)

mi xa tarē mô kud
CONT.PRS NOM.I become.INF more good
I'm getting better (and will continue to do so)

taro xa mô kud
become.PST NOM.I more good
I got better

tarē can also be used to mean 'it came to pass'. For example:

taro wā kamē ga
become.PST NOM.mā come.INF NOM.he
it came to pass that he came

12. The verbs *telē* and *mē*

There are two translations of 'to be' in *kōxō* – *telē* and *mē*. *telē* is used to say that one thing is a type of another, such as 'chairs are furniture' or 'John is a doctor'. *mē* has multiple uses.

12.1 *telē*

As already stated, *telē* is used to say that one thing is a type of another. In English, we do this by using indefinite articles or plurals e.g. 'cats are animals' or 'a cat is an animal'. In *kōxō*, we use *telē* with subspecific indefinite articles for such sentences. For example:

telē xā gat nā mōk
be.INF NOM.nā NOM.cat nā animal
a cat is an animal

Note that the first argument of *telē* is in the nominative and the second is unmarked. This is not the accusative, but rather a special use of the unmarked case. Note that *telē* is in the null tense because we are stating something about the concept of 'cat' that is inherently true of the concept and not limited to a particular time.

We can also say a specific thing is a type of another, for example:

telē ze gat nā mōk
be.INF NOM.se NOM.cat nā animal
the cat is an animal

The more general thing once again uses a subspecific article.

12.2 *mē*

The verb *mē* has a nominative argument and a plain argument. It should be understood that the plain argument is not accusative, but rather has a function specific to this verb.

mē with specifics and subspecifics

mē can be used with different specificity levels to show different kinds of relationship. For example:

mi xā parallelogram nā shape with four parallel sides
be.PRS NOM.nā parallelogram nā shape with four parallel sides
a parallelogram is a shape with four parallel sides

Here, a subspecific article is being used to show the concepts 'parallelogram' and 'shape with four parallel sides' are identical. We would use specific articles for non-identical concepts. For example:

mi xe parallelogram ne shape with sides that are each 5 cm long
be.PRS NOM.ne parallelogram ne shape with sides that are each 5 cm long
a parallelogram is a shape with sides that are each 5 cm long

Here, we are not equating the concept of 'parallelogram' to the concept of 'shape with sides that are 5 cm long'. We are saying that there is a specific parallelogram with sides that are 5 cm long, but not stating that parallelograms necessarily or by definition have sides that are 5 cm long.

Note that the case with subspecific articles does not have to be a word and its definition. It can equate two concepts neither of which consist of a single word. For example, the sentence

mi xā rhombus onas all of its angles are 90 degrees nā rectangle onas all of its sides are equal
be.PRS NOM.nā rhombus such.that all of its angles are 90 degree nā rectangle such.that all of its sides are equal
a rhombus all of whose angles are 90 degrees is a rectangle all of whose sides are equal

equates 'a rhombus all of whose angles are 90 degrees' with 'a rectangle all of whose sides are equal', both of these being equal to the concept of 'square'.

We can also see the difference between equations of subspecifics and equations of specifics in examples such as the following:

mi wot se suden
be.PRS NOM.what se score
What is the score?

mi wot sā suden
be.PRS NOM.what sā score
What is the score?

The former is the more common usage. An appropriate answer would be something like 3-0. The latter is a question that might be posed by something

who knows nothing about sports, and an appropriate answer would be an explanation of what the term 'score' means.

Another example is:

mi wot se minimum wage
be.PRS NOM.what se minimum.wage
What is the minimum wage?

mi wot sã minimum wage
be.PRS NOM.what sã minimum.wage
What is the minimum wage?

Similarly to the previous example, the first of the pair asks for the value of the minimum wage, and the second asks for the definition of the term 'minimum wage'.

We can also use definite articles. For example:

mi zã zũf sã person who rules the country
be.PRS NOM.sã NOM.king sã person who rules the country

Here, we are equating the concepts 'king' and 'person who rules the country' using subspecific articles.

mi ze zũf Charles
be.PRS NOM.se NOM.king Charles

Here, we are using specifics to say that the king happens to be Charles.

mi ze zũf se world chess champion
be.PRS NOM.se NOM.king se world.chess.champion

Here, we are using specifics to say that the king happens to be the world chess champion, without saying that being the king and being the world chess champion are the same thing or that the king must always be the world chess champion or vice versa.

mē with superspecifics

Superspecific articles can be used with *mē* to eliminate ambiguity. Let us consider some examples.

Example 1:

The phrase 'he thought the son was the father' can be translated as

kato ga mā mē zi son se father
think.PST NOM.he mā be.INF NOM.si NOM.son se father

or

kato ga mā mē ze son se father
think.PST NOM.he mā be.INF NOM.se son se father

The first translation is correct, the second makes no sense because it asserts that he thought he was the father even though he knew he was the son and vice versa.

Example 2:

The phrase 'I thought you were someone I knew' can be translated as

kato xa mā mē vu neves o kenē xa
think.PST NOM.I mā be.INF NOM.you SP.someone o know.INF NOM.I

or

kato xa mā mē vu nives o kenē xa
think.PST NOM.I mā be.INF NOM.you SPSP.someone o know.INF NOM.I

The first translation means 'I thought I knew you'. The second means 'I thought you were a person (who is not you) that I knew'.

Example 3:

The phrase 'I want to be the king' can be translated as

feli xa mē se sūf
want.PRS NOM.I be.INF se king

or

feli xa mē si sūf
want.PRS NOM.I be.INF si king

The first translation means 'I want to be the one who is king'. The second means 'I want to be who the king is'. For example, if the king is Mufasa, the second translation means 'I want to be Mufasa'.

13. Adverbs

13.1 Position of adverbial phrases

Adverbs and adverbial phrases in kōxō are placed before the verb and, if there is an auxiliary verb, between the main verb and auxiliary verb. For example:

lenden kino xa
slow.ADV go.PST NOM.I
I went slowly

mō xa pō lenden kinē
CONT.PST NOM.I so slow.ADV go.INF
I was going so slowly

13.2 Classification of adverbs by order and position

Adverbs that can function as adjectives are known as first-order adverbs. For example, *fast* (fast) is first-order because it can be used as an adverb, as in *fasten kinē* (go fast) or an adjective, as in *se faste man* (the fast man).

On the other hand, an adverb such as *tō* (too) is second-order because it can only be used as an adverb. It cannot be used as a verb or adjective.

We can also classify adverbs based on whether they may be placed before the auxiliary verb. Such adverbs are called pre-auxiliary adverbs.

13.2.1 First order adverbs

Adjectives in their coda form can be used as adverbs by placing them before another verb.

Adverbs have a distinct coda form, formed by the suffix *-en*. This is the equivalent of the suffix *-ly* in English. It reduces ambiguity. For example, we can distinguish between

se tē fasten kine man
se very fast.ADV go.COD man
the very quickly going man

se tē faste kine man
se very fast.COD go.COD man
the very quick, going man

13.2.2 Pre-auxiliary adverbs

A list of pre-auxiliary adverbs is given below. By definition, those without an entry in the 'adjectival coda form' column are second-order adverbs. Those with the cells for 'adverbial coda form' and 'adverbial non-coda form' merged into a single cell are considered to have neither an adverbial coda nor adverbial non-coda form, but simply an adverbial form.

English	Adjectival coda form	Adverbial coda form	Adverbial non-coda form
MISCELLANEOUS			
not, don't	-	kiu	kē
even	-	oben	obi
actually	somde	somdi	
only	nore	noi	
also	-	ami	
at all	-	xx	
MOOD			
<i>interrogative</i>	-	tun	
must (epistemic)	mose	mos	mosen
should (epistemic)	sude	sud	suden
might	mede	med	meden
FREQUENCY			
always	sunde	suned	sunden
never	kunde	kuned	kunden
often	taspe	tasep	taspen
seldom, hardly ever	nispe	nisep	nispen
sometimes	asimai	asima	asimen
TIME			
already	-	ane	
still	-	nan	
no longer, not any more	-	kūmō	
again	-	agi	
just (as in 'just now')	pone	pon	
recently	xx	xx	
immediately	xx	xx	
soon	xx	xx	
later	xx	xx	

supposed to
will (evidential) - 'did you copy it down wrong?' 'I won't have done'

13.2.2.1 Notes on pre-auxiliary adverbs

Some of the coda forms in the table are worth looking at in more detail. The coda forms of mood and frequency are summarised below:

mose - necessary

sude - no translation

mede - possible

sunde - eternal, permanent

kunde - no translation

taspe - frequent

nispe - infrequent

asimai - occasional

In English, words such as 'must' and 'necessary', 'always' and 'permanent' etc. have related meanings but are etymologically unrelated. In *kōxō*, they very much are etymologically related, one being a coda form of the other.

The adverbs of time are especially strange to an English speaker. We would say 'the upcoming exam', 'the parade that happened just now', 'the former president', but not 'the soon exam', 'the just now parade' or 'the no longer president'. All of these constructions, however, are legal in *kōxō*.

Note that although all the adverbs of time in this table are pre-auxiliary adverbs, there is a notable adverb of time that is not a pre-auxiliary adverb and hence not included in this table. That adverb is *tol*, which means 'about to' or 'on the verge of'. For example:

mi xa tol kefē

CONT.PRS NOM.I *about.to eat*.INF

I am about to eat

mō xa tol kefē

CONT.PST NOM.I *about.to eat*.INF

I was about to eat

kē

kē means 'not'. *kē* is both a pre-auxiliary adverb and a second-order adverb and it is the only second-order adverb to have a non-determiner coda form, *kiu*. It is the coda form that is most often used, being used before verbs in the way 'do not' is used in English. For example

kiū mi xa kinē

not.ADV CONT.PRS NOM.I go.INF
I'm not going

The non-coda form is used similarly to how the prefix *un-* is used in English. For example:

kē naturalen kori zen
not natural.ADV happen.PRS NOM.it
It happens unnaturally

kiu naturalen kori zen
not.ADV natural.COD happen.PRS NOM.it
It does not happen naturally

naturalen kiu kori zen
natural.ADV not.ADV happen.PRS NOM.it
It naturally does not happen

And an example with adjectives:

se kē feden kude man
se not usual good.COD man
the unusually good man

se kiu feden kude man
se not.ADV usual good.COD man
the not usually good man (i.e. the man who is not usually good)

se kē fedne kude man
se not usual.COD good.COD man
the unusual, good man

obi

This is the translation of the word 'even'. Note that this can also be used as a **premarker** e.g.

magi xa obi ka
like.PRS NOM.I even he
I even like him

which differs subtly from

obi magi xa ka
even like.PRS NOM.I he

in that the latter it is the liking as opposed to not liking that is noteworthy and in the former it is that he is one of those who are liked that is noteworthy. *obi* combines with other adverbs to form set phrases:

obi kiū = not even/ don't even
obi la/ obi lō = even if

ami
ami means 'also', 'too' and 'as well'. It can also be used as a **premarker** e.g.

magi xa ami ka
like.PRS NOM.I also he

meaning 'he is another of the things I like', as opposed to

ami magi xa ka
also like.PRS NOM.I he

which means 'I like him (in addition to finding him annoying sometimes etc)'.

noi
noi means 'only' as in 'I only like one'. It is used to emphasise a lack of additional things and is not to be confused with *tābō* which is used to emphasise the weakness of a statement. It can also be used as an adjective, as in *se noi menek* (the only person).

tun
Turns a statement into a question. For example

tun magi vu sen?
tun like.PRS NOM.you it?
Do you like it?

Note that *tun* is used only to transform statements into questions, not to mark sentences that are already questions. For example, *magi vu mot?* ('What do you like?') is already a question because it contains *mot* (what), so we would not say *tun magi vu mot?*

mos, sud

mos means 'must' and *sud* means 'should'. In *kōxō*, there are two different words for 'should' and two different words for 'must' - the epistemic and deontic forms. Only the epistemic forms are pre-auxiliary adverbs. The deontic forms are modal verbs and are discussed in section 11.11. The difference between the epistemic and deontic forms is that the epistemic forms relate to the truth of a statement whereas the deontic forms relate to the rightness or appropriateness of a statement. For example, 'it must be true' (because the evidence implies it) would use the epistemic 'must'; 'I must do that' (because I am obliged to) would use the deontic 'must'. Examples of *mos* and *sud* in use:

namosen kino ga
na-must.ADV go.PST NOM.he
He must have gone

nasuden mi zen onde se sageb
na-should.ADV CONT.PRS NOM.it under se bed
It should be under the bed

Note that the conjunctive forms of the adverbs are used in the examples above. These forms are explained in section 13.3.

med
med means 'might'. For example,

nameden pari xa sen
na-might.ADV do.PRS NOM.I it
I might be doing it

nameden paro xa sen
na-might.ADV do.PST NOM.I it
I might have done it

Note that the conjunctive form of the adverb is used in the example above. This form is explained in section 13.3.

Note also that there are two words for 'possible' in *kōxō*. One is *mede* and the other is *kanos*, which comes from the epistemic 'can' *kanē*. *mede* means that something is possible and could actually be happening. *kanos* can be used even if something is definitely not happening. For example, if we translate the phrase 'possible username' with *mede*, this means that given the information we have someone may actually have this username. If we translate it with *kanos*, we could use it to refer to a username we are sure does not actually exist in the

sense that no-one has this username, but is nevertheless in the valid format and hence is available as a username. Note that *mede* is essentially epistemic but we have not defined a deontic 'might' because it would have the same meaning as the deontic 'can' *kūvē*.

suned, kuned

These adverbs can be used with verbs in the null, past or future tense. For example:

sunden parē xa sen
always.ADV do.INF NOM.I it
I always do it

sunden paro xa sen *????*
always.ADV do.PST NOM.I it
I have always done it

sunden parasi xa sen
always.ADV do.FUT NOM.I it
I will always do it

pon

pon means 'just' as in 'I've just been there'. Unlike in English, it is not typically accompanied by the perfect aspect. For example, 'I've just been there' would be translated

pon mō xa sē
just CONT.PST NOM.I there

not

pon mari xa sē
just be.PRF.PST NOM.I there

and

pon paro xa sen
just do.PST NOM.I it

not

pon parari xa sen

just do.PRF.PRS NOM.I it

pon is not to be confused with the other translation of 'just', *tābō*.

nan

nan means 'still' as in 'I haven't finished. I'm still doing it', but not as in 'Even though he warned me not to, I still did it', which would be translated using *tumes sen* (anyway).

ane

ane means 'already'. It is often used with the perfect aspect, as in:

ane parari xa sen

already do.PRF.PRS NOM.I it

I've already done it

ane pararo xa sen

already do.PRF.PST NOM.I it

I'd already done it

It can also be used with the continuous or progressive particle. For example:

ane mō xa parē sen

already CONT.PST NOM.I do.INF it

I was already doing it

agi

agi is the word for 'again'. Like *son*, it is often used with the perfect, progressive or continuous aspects. For example:

agi parari xa sen

again do.PRF.PRS NOM.I it

I've done it again

mi xa agi parē sen

CONT.PRS NOM.I again do.INF it

I'm doing it again

But can also be used without auxiliary verbs. For example:

agi paro xa sen

again do.PST NOM.I it

I did it again

modal combinations that do not exist in english e.g. 'should would'

13.2.3 Second-order adverbs

kōxō	English	Determiner form?
DEGREE		
tē	very/ very much	yes
pō	so/ so much	-
tō	too/ too much	-
pā	not very much	yes
pōpā	so little	yes
tōpā	too little	yes
mabi	enough	yes
nel	completely, totally	yes
kis	quite	-
kusek	almost	-
kaum	hardly	-
tābō	just (i.e. only)	-
COMPARISON		
mo	more	yes
pōmo	so much more	yes
tōmo	too much more	yes
lê	less	yes
pōlê	so much less	yes
tōlê	too much less	yes
nê	most	-
len	least	-

13.2.3.1 Notes on second-order adverbs

tē, pō, tō

Earlier, it was explained that *pō, tō, kū,* and *kasai* are applied to verbs and adjectives in the same way. The same also applied to *tē*. For example:

mi zen tē naf

CONT.PRS NOM.*it very red*

It is very red

tē magi xa ka

very like.PRS NOM.I he
I like him very much

The previous example can be translated more literally as 'I very like him'.
pō and *tō* are often used with *mā*. For example:

mi zen pō naf mā...
CONT.PRS NOM.it so.much red mā...
It is so red that...

pō magi xa ka mā...
so.much like.PRS NOM.I he mā...
I like him so much that...

mi zen tō naf mā...
CONT.PRS NOM.it too.much red mā...
It is too red to...

tō magi xa ka mā...
too.much like.PRS NOM.I he mā...
I like him too much to...

mabi

This means 'enough'. It is often used with *mā*. For example

mi zen mabi naf mā...
CONT.PRS NOM.it enough red mā...
It is red enough to...

It can also be used as an adjective and a determiner.

tābō

This means 'just', as in

tābō mi xa mirē
just CONT.PRS NOM.I see.INF
I'm just looking

It can also be used as a **premarker**. For example, we might say

tābō feli xa nā puk. kiū nezi xa nā puk.
just want.PRS NOM.I nā book. not.ADV need.PRS NOM.I nā book.

I just want a book. I don't need a book.

But we would say

feli xa tãbō nã puk. kiū feli xa kuneb
want.PRS NOM.I just nã book. not.ADV want.PRS NOM.I money.
I just want a book. I don't want money.

mô, mon, lê, len

mô and *lê* are often accompanied by *sū*. For example

mi ga mô kom sū na
CONT.PRS NOM.he more big than I
He is bigger than me

13.3 Conjunctive adverbs

A typical first order adverb can be turned into a conjunctive adverb using the prefix *na-*. For example:

nafednen paro xa sen
na-usual.ADV do.PST NOM.I it
I usually did it (usually, I did it)

fednen paro xa sen
usual.ADV do.PST NOM.I it
I usually did it (I did it in a usual way)

nalegosen osdako xa ka
na-legal.ADV execute.PST NOM.I he
I legally executed him (legally, I executed him)

legosen osdako xa ka
na-legal.ADV execute.PST NOM.I he
I legally executed him (I executed him in a legal way)

nasampen paro xa sen
na-simple.ADV do.PST NOM.I it
I simply did it (I just did it)

sampen paro xa sen
simple.ADV do.PST NOM.I it
I simply did it (I did it in a simple way)

In particular, modal adverbs are usually in the conjunctive form. For example:

namosen paro xa sen
na-must.ADV do.PST NOM. I it
I must have done it

mosen paro xa sen
must.ADV do.PST NOM. I it
I did it necessarily

Note that the equivalents of many words that are classed as conjunctive adverbs in English are not classed as conjunctive adverbs in *kōxō*. For example, *temō* (therefore) is classed as a conjunctive adverb in English but a marker in *kōxō* (or a conjunction???) because in a sentence of the form *X temō Y*, *temō* marks the relationship of *Y* to *X* rather than modifying *Y*. This is true even in sentences beginning with *temō* such as *temō, paro xa sen* (therefore, I did it) because it implies a relationship to another phrase even if that phrase is not explicitly stated.

14. Word formation

14.1 Compounding

Both verbs and nouns can be formed by compounding. For example, the verb *xxx* (to insulate) is formed from the nouns *xxx* (layer) and *xxx* (shield). The verb *xxx* (to compete) is formed from the verbs *xxx* (win) and *xxx* (try). Examples of nouns formed by compounding include *xxx* (telescope, literally 'star pipe'), and *xxx* (balloon, literally 'air sphere').

14.2 Rendaku

Rendaku is a word borrowed from Japanese and refers to consonant mutations in compound words. These are used in *kōxō* to hide the etymology of the compound. For example:

me+nakē (to+fight) = *mexakē* (to attack)
mēhō+kol (far+eye) = *mēhōgol* (telescope)

In each of the above compounds, the initial consonant of the second component of the compound has mutated in the same way as consonants are mutated to form the nominative case.

It should be noted that *rendaku* is only used in compounds when the compound does not have the literal meaning of its components. In fact, there are cases where there are two compounds with the same components, one of which has the literal meaning and hence does not use *rendaku*, and the other of which does not have the literal meaning and hence does use *rendaku*. For example:

korenakē = to fight in front of
korexakē = to defend

14.3 Deriving verbs by prefixing a marker

It is possible to derive verbs by prefixing a marker either to an already existing verb or to a root that cannot be used without a prefix. For example, the verb *engosē* (to include) consists of the marker prefix form *en* (in) prefixed to *gosē*, which has no meaning on its own.

Kōxō uses marker prefixes in situations where English would use phrasal verbs. For example, 'I went in' would be translated as *enkino xa*. These English phrasal verbs cannot be nominalised, which is a very awkward and inconvenient feature of the English language. The best we can do to nominalise English verbs such as 'give up' and 'find out' is to make awkward, non-standard constructions such as

'giver upper' and 'finder outer' or to find a Latin equivalent such as 'investigator'. However, *kōxō* verbs with marker prefixes can easily be nominalised.

14.4 Deriving verbs, adjectives, and adverbs using special affixes

In addition to markers, there are some affixes that are used only with verbs. These are:

DERIVATIVES OF MEKE AND TARE	
-ame	causative prefix e.g. <i>foskame</i> = freeze (transitive), <i>kētidame</i> = untie, <i>kaisekname</i> = disconnect (transitive), <i>mosoftame</i> = soften (transitive)
-etre	become e.g. <i>fosketre</i> = freeze (intransitive), <i>kēseknadetre</i> = disconnect (intransitive), <i>mosoftetre</i> = soften (intransitive)
DERIVATIVES OF TŌ	
tō-	Indicates that something is done in excess. e.g. <i>tōestimate</i> = overestimate. Note that though this is equivalent to the English prefix 'over', the <i>kōxō</i> word for 'over', <i>ōve</i> , is used differently as a prefix, indicating an elevated state but not excess. e.g. <i>ōveestimate</i> = to estimate highly (but not necessarily to overestimate), <i>ōvemagē</i> = to prefer (not 'to like too much')
tunde-	Contraction of <i>tō onde</i> e.g. <i>tundestate</i> = understate
tuve-	Contraction of <i>tō ōve</i> e.g. <i>tuvestate</i> = overstate
PREFIXES OF NEGATION	
kai-	Makes a verb into its opposite e.g. <i>kaikimē</i> = disagree. Equivalent to the English prefix <i>anti-</i> .
kon-	Transitive prefix used to indicate action that reverses or ends some state. Equivalent to English <i>un-</i> or <i>dis-</i> . e.g. <i>konbedē</i> = <i>kon</i> +*ask = to cancel, <i>kondakē</i> = <i>kon</i> +*take = to give up, to renounce, <i>konkausē</i> = <i>kon</i> +cause = to prevent
kun-	Intransitive prefix used to indicate action that reverses or ends some state. Equivalent to English <i>un-</i> or <i>dis-</i> . e.g. <i>kundep_te</i> = <i>kun</i> +*try = surrender, <i>kunform</i> = <i>kun</i> +form = to subside, to disintegrate, to disperse
PREFIXES OF DIRECTION	
mau-	Means 'outwards in all directions'. Used with verbs

	linked to expansion.
san-	Means 'inwards in all directions'. Used with verbs linked to contraction.
len-	Indicates that the subject is actively bringing the object towards itself
lon-	Indicates that the object is moving towards the subject, with the subject playing a passive role
nū-	Indicates that the object is moving from the subject
nusen-	Used to form verbs where the object is moving 'away from' the subject, rather than simply moving 'from' the subject. For example, <i>nūmandē</i> means 'send' but <i>nusenmandē</i> means 'send away'.
	forward, forth
	back
MARKERS USED AS PREFIXES WITH SPECIFIC MEANINGS OTHER THAN THEIR LITERAL MEANING	
me-	Indicates reaching, arrival, completion e.g. <i>megage</i> = achieve
en-	Modifies the verb to make it an act of internal thought e.g. <i>enlekē</i> = recognise (that something is true)
os-	Modifies the verb to make it an act of communication e.g. <i>oslekē</i> = admit
an-	e.g. <i>anmirē</i> = look (as in 'it looks like'), <i>ankūdē</i> = sound (as in 'it sounds like')
on-	e.g. <i>onmirē</i> = look, <i>onkūdē</i> = listen
AFFIXES CONVERTING FROM ONE WORD CLASS TO ANOTHER	
-anē	Turns a noun into a transitive verb e.g. <i>hammeranē</i> = to hammer, <i>poisonanē</i> = to poison
	Turns an intransitive verb into a transitive verb e.g. <i>tonanē</i> = to turn
-ustē	Turns a noun into an intransitive non-stative verb e.g. <i>kaskustē</i> = to crack
-umē	Turns a noun into an intransitive stative verb e.g. <i>stepumē</i> = to step, <i>dropumē</i> = to drip
-un	Turns a noun into an adjective e.g. <i>kaskun</i> = cracked
na-	Turns an adverb into a conjunctive adverb
MISCELLANEOUS PREFIXES	
tove-	together
pan-	apart
kami-	Makes the verb reflexive
nes-	Intensifies the verb e.g. <i>nesoskatē</i> = assert, <i>nespedē</i> =

	demand
fen-	Softens the verb e.g. <i>fenoskatē</i> = propose, <i>fenpedē</i> = request
ti-	Indicates negative connotations e.g. <i>tigasmē</i> = <i>ti+*claim</i> = accuse
mis-	Indicates that something is being done incorrectly. Same as the English prefix mis-
onō-	Indicates that an action is being done correctly. The opposite of <i>mis-</i>
ari-	Similar to the English prefix <i>re-</i> where an action is done again due to the first attempt being inadequate e.g. 'rewrite'. Translations of <i>re-</i> where previous attempts were adequate are just translated using <i>las</i> ('again').
esi-	Means 'to the fullest possible extent' e.g. <i>esinomē</i> = <i>esi+use</i> = to use up
tanso-	Equivalent to the English 'trans'
kin-	Means 'from nothing' e.g. <i>kinmekē</i> = <i>kin+make</i> = to make up, to invent, <i>kingamē</i> = <i>kin+*come</i> = to appear
seri-	Means 'at more or less regular intervals' e.g. <i>serijerk</i> = jolty/ jerky (stopping and starting again at regular intervals), <i>xxx</i> = intersperse, <i>xxx</i> = intermittent, <i>xxx</i> = stutter
siudo-	Equivalent to the English prefix <i>pseudo-</i>
supe-	Equivalent to English <i>ultra-</i> , <i>mega-</i> , <i>hyper-</i> , <i>super-</i> etc.
ten-	Indicates that the object is inside the subject
	Makes the argument of a locative marker the object of the verb e.g. <i>xxx</i> = I loaded it (into the truck) vs. <i>xxx</i> = I loaded the truck, <i>xxx</i> = I paid the money vs. I paid the man, <i>xxx</i> = I relieved his suffering vs. <i>xxx</i> = I relieved him (of his suffering)
MISCELLANEOUS SUFFIXES	
-os	Means 'pertaining to'. Equivalent to the English -ic, -al -ical, and -ous.
-esek	Means 'similar to'. Equivalent to the English -esque, -oid, -ine, and -like
-fol	Means 'full of'. Equivalent to the English -ful
-ekan	Equivalent of English suffix <i>-able</i>
-ened	Indicates a tendency to do the action or be in the state to which the verb refers e.g. <i>ondakened</i> = accepting as in 'he is very accepting', <i>lovened</i> = loving as in 'he is a loving person'

14.4.1 Notes on the special derivational affixes

-amē

-amē is the causative suffix. For example:

foskami xa se mis
frozen.CAUS.PRS NOM.I se water
I freeze the water

Note that there is also a causative auxiliary verb *mekē* (see section 11.11). For example:

meki xa mā mē ze wis fosek
make.PRS NOM.I mā CONT NOM.se NOM.water frozen
I make that the water is frozen

-etrē

-etrē means 'become'. For example:

andi xa kaltetrē
PROG.PRS NOM.I cold.become.INF
I'm getting cold

kaltetro xa
cold.become.PST NOM.I
I got cold

-etrē can only be prefixed to single words to derive new words from existing ones. In particular, it cannot be used before adverbial phrases or as a verb on its own. In such situations, we use *tarē* instead, which is the verbal equivalent of -etrē (see also section 11.11). For example:

taro xa mā tē moz
become.PST NOM.I mā very hot
I got very hot

taro xa mā se sūf
become.PST NOM.I mā se king
I became the king

14.5 Deriving nouns using special affixes

The following table lists affixes that are used to form new nouns.

fenō-	Prefixing this to X creates a noun representing whether X is true e.g. <i>depends ze venōfasen gô claim on...</i> = 'the truth of his claim depends on...' (i.e. 'whether his claim is true or false depends on...')
-ed	Diminutive e.g. <i>tog</i> = dog, <i>toged</i> = little dog
-ag	Augmentative e.g. <i>fak</i> = house, <i>fakag</i> = mansion
-sed	Used with certain markers to form nominalisations. These are <i>ensed</i> (inside), <i>ossed</i> (outside), <i>onsed</i> (surface), <i>labsed</i> (front), <i>massed</i> (back), <i>ondesed</i> (bottom i.e. the side underneath), <i>nadsed</i> (bottom as in 'bottom of the ocean'), <i>baised</i> (side) and <i>morised</i> (surroundings). These are used in phrases such as 'the inside of the box', but not 'I am inside', which is just translated as <i>mi xa en sen</i> (literally 'I am in it').
	Equivalent to -ary, as in 'commentary'.

14.6 Deriving nouns from verbs using case

Each case has an associated 'nominalising suffix', as shown in the following table:

	sing.	pl.
nominative	-ai	-aien
accusative	-on	-onen
mā	-im	-imen
arg. of adjective	-us	-usen

For example:

se kefai = 'the eater'

se kinai = 'the goer'

se somanon = 'the thing perceived'

se somanim = 'the perception' (as in 'my perception is that...' not 'the power of perception', which would be translated with the gerund).

-us functions as a nominaliser for both adjectives and adverbs. Hence we have

se fastus = 'the fast thing'/ 'the fast one'

and also

se fastus ga = 'what he was doing quickly'

These nominalisations can be conjugated. For example

mō ze xafus kom
CONT.PST NOM.se NOM.red-us big
the red one was big

These prefixes are not used with conjugated forms of verbs, with constructions involving *i* being preferable. For example, 'the one who ate' is translated

ka i kefo
he NOM.o eat.PST

rather than

se kefoai
se eat.PST-ai

A verb can be nominalised within a larger phrase without the rest of the phrase changing. For example:

se kakai se puk
se write.ai se book
the writer of the book

se falan ze empire
se fall.an NOM.se NOM.empire
the fall of the empire

When an adjective is nominalised, the associated noun phrase becomes nominative. For example:

se kūkom ze vak
se how.much-big NOM.se NOM.house
the size of the house

14.7 Coda forms derived using markers and nouns

Sometimes marked expressions can be converted into coda form verbs. For example:

mi ze buk en kōxō
CONT.PRS NOM.se NOM.book in kōxō
the book is in kōxō

se enkōxon puk
se in-kōxō.COD book
the book that is in kōxō (lit. 'the in kōxō book')

mi ze wan ovi fak
CONT.PRS NOM.se NOM.man without house
the man is homeless

se ovifake man
se without-house-COD man
the homeless man

15. Temporal and locative phrases

There are certain words that are, in a certain sense, like ‘pronouns’ of space and time. Since they are quite special and frequently used, they deserve separate treatment. They are shown in the table below.

ENGLISH	KŌXŌ NOUN	KŌXŌ CODA FORM
here	ki	kire
there	sē	sere
over there	asē	asere
now	nau	naue
then	nos	nose
today	kais	kaise
yesterday	monev	monve
tomorrow	sevai	sevaie

In English grammar, a phrase such as ‘It is there’ is interpreted to be using ‘there’ as an adverb. Kōxō also has such phrases, but I prefer to interpret it as using ‘there’ as a noun with the marker *an* omitted for the sake of brevity. Similarly, in a phrase such as *kini xa sē* (I go there), I prefer to interpret *sē* as a noun with the marker *me* omitted rather than as an adverb.

Many phrases consisting of more than one word function in the same way. For example, *sun XXX* (this afternoon).

The coda forms of these words result in constructions quite alien to what we have in English. For example:

se naue XXX = the current leader

se nose XXX = the then leader

se kire fak = the house here

16. Identifiers

The identifiers are a small class of words including translations of ‘what’, ‘who’ etc. *kū-* and *kasai* were introduced earlier in section 10.8.2. Each identifier has an interrogative and non-interrogative form, with some having both specific and super-specific non-interrogative forms. They are shown in the table below.

English	Marker	Nominalisation			
		Non-interrogative		Interrogative	
		nom.	prep.	nom.	prep.
what	-	vot	fot	wot	mot
who	-	ves	fes	wes	mes
where	fê	vê	fê	wê	mê
when	fon	von	fon	won	mon
which	-	velke	felke	welke	melke
how/ how much	-	kū-	gū-	-	kasai

16.1 The marker forms of 'where' and 'when'

'When' and 'where' have distinct marker forms. These are used to form relative clauses. For example:

se fak fê fōni ga
se house where live.PRS NOM.he
the house where he lives

xxx
the time when we went there

However, they should not be used as **conjunctions** to link non-relative clauses. For example, 'he greeted me when I arrived' and 'We swam where the water was warm' would not use the marker form.

Unlike in English, 'who' and 'which' cannot be used as markers. For example, we would not say something like 'the man who did it' or 'the pool which I swam in'.

16.2 Interrogative forms

The interrogative forms are used to ask questions. Unlike in English, the word order of questions does not differ from other types of sentence. For example, in the question *mi wot fô nām?* (what is your name?) *wot* is in the same position as someone's name is in a statement such as *mi xô xām anthony*.

These forms can be thought of as nouns and can be used with markers. For example, the interrogative forms of 'where' and 'when' can be used in sentences such as:

andi vu kinē me mē
PROG.PRS NOM.you go.INF to INT.where
Where are you going?

but in situations where the marker *an* (at) would be used, they are dropped. For example:

nafko vu (an) mē
swim.PST NOM.you (at) INT.where
(at) where did you swim?

nafko vu (an) mon
swim.PST NOM.you (at) INT.when
(at) when did you swim?

16.3 Non-interrogative forms

Non-interrogative forms of 'where' and 'when' are used as nouns in sentences such as

mi vê fōni ga kud
CONT.PRS NOM.where live.PRS NOM.he good
where he lives is good

They are also used in sentences where it may be less obvious that they are acting as nouns, such as

kino xa me fê mō ze wis fām
go.PST NOM.I to where CONT.PST NOM.se NOM.water warm
I went (to) where the water was warm

As with the interrogative forms, in situations where the noun-like non-interrogative form should technically be used with *an* (at), the *an* is dropped. For example:

nafko xa (an) fê mō ze wis fām
swim.PST NOM.I (at) where CONT.PST NOM.se NOM.water warm
I swam (at) where the water was warm

16.4 Identifiers and specificity

There is nothing special about how specificity applies to identifiers and perhaps it does not need to be commented on. Nevertheless, the following examples are provided:

feli ga [nafkē fê mē ze wis fām]
want.PRS NOM.he [swim.INF where CONT NOM.se NOM.water warm]

The above means 'he wants to swim where the water is warm', where he knows that the water is warm there. Contrast this with

feli ga [nafkē minfê mē ze wis fām]
want.PRS NOM.he [swim.INF min-where CONT NOM.se NOM.water warm]

which means that he wants to swim in a certain place, which happens to be where the water is warm although he is not necessarily aware that the water is warm there.

And similar examples could be provided for 'when'.

16.5 Using identifiers before accusative phrases

16.5.1 Using *fot* and *mot* before accusative phrases

Consider the sentence 'I know what he knows'. This is ambiguous. It could either mean 'I know the same thing as him' or 'I know the answer to the question 'What does he know?'' In *kōxō*, this is not ambiguous. The former is translated as

keni xa sen o keni ga
know.PRS NOM.I it o know.PRS NOM.he

The latter is translated as

keni xa fot sen o keni ga
know.PRS NOM.I what it o know.PRS NOM.he

The difference between these sentences is that the second sentence uses *fot* (what) before *sen o*. *fot* is behaving similarly to a preposition here, with *sen o...* essentially being in the accusative case, although this case is not marked in *kōxō*.

We can extend this example. The sentence

keni vu mot o keni ga
know.PRS NOM.you INT.what o know.PRS NOM.he

means 'What do you know that he knows?' Or, since this translation is ambiguous, 'What knowledge do you have in common with him?' Whereas the sentence

keni vu mot sen o keni ga
know.PRS you INT.what it o know.PRS NOM.he

can also be translated as 'What do you know that he knows?' but this time means 'What are you sure that he knows?' or 'What is it that you know he knows?'

16.5.2 Using *fes*, *felke*, and *kū*- before accusative phrases

Other identifiers can be used before accusative phrases in the same way.

fes
keni xa fes se man
know.PRS NOM.I who se man
I know who the man is

keni xa fes fu
know.PRS NOM.I who you
I know who you are

keni xa fes ka opō o mi vu pālē
know.PRS NOM.I who he about o CONT.PRS NOM.you talk.INF
I know who you are talking about

felke
keni xa felke se nê kome pol
know.PRS NOM.I which se most big-COD ball
I know which is the biggest ball

keni xa felke se nêkomai afel se polen
know.PRS NOM.I which se most-big-ai of se ball.PL
I know which is the biggest of the balls

kū
keni xa kū magi vu ka
know.PRS NOM.I how.much like.PRS NOM.you he

I know how much you like him

16.5.3 Using *fê* and *fon* before accusative phrases

As well as using *fot* before *se* or *sen*, 'when' or 'where' can also be used before them and other 'accusative' phrases and clauses. For example:

keni xa fê paro vu sen

know.PRS NOM.I where do.PST NOM.you it

I know where you did it

keni xa fon paro vu sen

know.PRS NOM.I when do.PST NOM.you it

I know when you did it

keni xa fê sen mus o kamo ga

know.PRS NOM.I where it from o come.PST NOM.he

I know where he came from

keni xa fon sen until o fādo ga

know.PRS NOM.I when it until o wait.PST NOM.he

I know what time he waited until

17. Markers: part II

17.1 Explanative markers

In *kōxō*, words such as ‘because’ are translated using ‘explanative markers’, also called explanatives. The corresponding interrogative form of each of these words is formed by adding the suffix *-mot* (what). For example, *kā* is one possible translation of ‘because’ and *kāmot* means ‘why’.

The usage of the words ‘how’ and ‘why’ in English is often ambiguous, or at least not sufficiently specific. In *kōxō*, there are several explanatives and hence several translations of ‘how’ and ‘why’, allowing more precise meanings to be expressed.

To understand the differences between the explanatives, let us consider some examples.

Firstly, consider the sentence ‘why do you want to do that?’ This question has several possible interpretations. One possible answer to this question is ‘because I saw someone else doing it’. This answer refers to the cause that prompted the statement to become true. This is translated using *kā*, which is used for causes, although it is possible to be more specific and use *tikā*, which refers to causes that prompt change. Another is ‘because the thought of doing so is stimulating the pleasure centres in my brain’. This answer refers to the underlying mechanism that enables desire to exist. It is also translated using *kā*, although it is possible to be more specific and use *mēkā*, which refers to a cause that must coexist with its effect such that the effect will cease if the cause ceases. Another is ‘because I will get a reward’. This refers to the motivation for performing the action. It is translated using *para*, which can also be translated as ‘in order to’. Note that *para* is also used to translate ‘for’ in phrases like ‘ovens are for cooking’.

Let us consider yet another example: ‘why is Tokyo the world’s largest urban area?’ An answer involving *tikā* could be ‘because the government encouraged people to move there’ or ‘because Japan’s mountainous geography forces the population to concentrate in a few areas’. We could also provide an answer using *pā*. If the question is answered with *pā*, it could be translated either as ‘why is Tokyo the world’s largest urban area?’ or ‘how is Tokyo the world’s largest urban area?’ A possible answer would be something like ‘because it has the most people’.

Now for a final example: ‘how do you sleep?’ One possible answer is ‘I sleep using ear plugs’. This refers to the method by which something is achieved. This is translated using *fara*. Another answer is ‘I sleep lightly’. This refers to the

manner in which you sleep, not how the act of sleep is accomplished. It is translated using *lau*. And if the question is something like ‘How do you sleep? I hear you pacing around every night’, we could even translate it using *pā*.

So, to summarise:

kā – marks a cause

tikā – marks a ‘prompting cause’

mēkā – marks an ‘underlying cause’

pā – marks evidence or an explanation of something being true when there is evidence to the contrary. It can also mean ‘in that’ or ‘in the sense that’.

lau – marks the manner in which something is done

fara – marks the means of accomplishing something

para – marks an end or motivation

Below is table showing the explanatives with their interrogative forms and translations of each.

Original word	Original translation	Word with -mot	New translation	Literal translation
<i>kā</i>	because	<i>kāmot</i>	why	because what
<i>pā</i>	in that, in the sense that	<i>pāmot</i>	how, why, in what way	in what, in what sense
<i>lau</i>	-	<i>laumot</i>	how	-
<i>fara</i>	by	<i>faramot</i>	how	by what
<i>para</i>	in order to	<i>paramot</i>	why	in order to what

Nominalisations of explanatives are shown in the table below.

<i>kaie</i>	cause, reason
<i>paie</i>	-
<i>laue</i>	manner, way
<i>farai</i>	method, way
<i>parai</i>	purpose, reason

Note that *kā* and *pā* are often used with *mā*. For example:

paro xa sen kā ka

do.PST NOM.I it kā he

I did it because of him

paro xa sen kā mā toldo ga nem parē sen
do.PST NOM.I it kā mā tell.PST NOM.he I.DAT do.INF it
I did it because he told me to

mi zen palo pā sô sampan
CONT.PRS NOM.it beautiful pā its simple.NZ
It is beautiful in its simplicity

mi zen palo pā mā mi zen sampe
CONT.PRS NOM.it beautiful pā mā CONT.PRS NOM.it simple
It is beautiful in that it is simple

kā and *pā* also have counterfactual forms. The counterfactual form of *kā* is *kui*. The counterfactual form of *pā* is *pui*.

Example 1:

magi xa sen kiū kā magi ga sen
like.PRS NOM.I it not.ADV kā like.PRS NOM.he it
I don't like it just because he likes it (but he does like it)

magi xa sen kiū kui magi ga sen
like.PRS NOM.I it not.ADV kui like.PRS NOM.he it
I don't like it just because he likes it (and it isn't even true that he likes it)

Example 2:

mi zen palo kiū pui mā mi zen complex. mi zen palo pā mā mi zen sampe
CONT.PRS NOM.it beautiful not.ADV pui mā CONT.PRS NOM.it complex. CONT.PRS
NOM.it beautiful pā mā CONT.PRS NOM.it simple
It is not beautiful in that it is complex. It is beautiful in that it is simple.

kā and *pā* can also be modified using the prefix *min*. The effect of this can be interpreted as raising the level of nesting or as putting the marked clause before the unmarked clause. For example:

kiū magi xa sen minkā magi ga sen
not.ADV like.PRS NOM.I it min-kā like.PRS NOM.he it
I don't like it, because he likes it/ because he likes it, I don't like it

17.2 Using explanatives before accusative phrases

Explanatives with the *-vot* suffix can be used before case markers in a similar way to identifiers. For example:

keni xa paravot paro ga sen
know.PRS NOM.I paravot do.PST NOM.he it
I know why he did it

keni xa lauvot tenkē ga
know.PRS NOM.I lauvot think.INF NOM.he
I know how he thinks

17.3 Nominalisation of explanatives and identifiers using determiners

Most explanatives and identifiers can be nominalised using certain determiners. For example, the table below shows nominalisations using *ne-*. The other determiners that can be used are the other indefinite articles and *nulu* and its forms.

<i>kōxō</i>	<i>English</i>
nevot	something
neves	someone
nevê	somewhere
nevon	at some point (literally 'somewhen')
nekā	for some reason (cause)
nepā	in some sense
nelau	somehow (manner)
nefara	somehow (means)
nepara	for some reason (end, motivation)

neves can also sometimes be translated as the English pronoun 'one', as in 'when one is driving a car, one must observe traffic regulations'. In English, 'one' is not used very much and tends to be replaced by 'you', as in 'when you are driving a car, you must observe traffic regulations', which can be ambiguous because in these contexts 'you' means something else to what it normally does but the sentence still makes sense if the common meaning of 'you' is used. In *kōxō*, this is not the case and the *kōxō* word for 'you' (*fu*) is never used for this purpose.

17.4 Boolean markers

The Boolean markers are shown in the table below:

wa	AND
tê	OR
tô	XOR

They can be used to form statements, either without modification or with the adverb *ede*, or to form questions with either the question marker *tun* or *wô*. For example:

feli xa se nafus tê se toblus
want.PRS NOM.I se red.us or se blue.us
I want the red one or the blue one or both

ede feli xa se nafus tê se toblus
ede want.PRS NOM.I se red.us or se blue.us
one or both of the statements 'I want the red one' or 'I want the blue one is true'

tun feli vu se nafus tê se toblus
tun want.PRS NOM.you se red.us or se blue.us
Is it true that you want the red one or the blue one or both?

tun ede feli vu se nafus tê se toblus
tun ede want.PRS NOM.you se red.us or se blue.us
Is it true that one or both of the statements 'you want the red one' or 'you want the blue one' is true?

wô feli vu se nafus tê se toblus
wô want.PRS NOM.you se red.us or se blue.us
Which do you want - the red one or the blue one?

wô ede feli vu se nafus tê se toblus
wô ede want.PRS NOM.you se red.us or se blue.us
Which is true - that you want the red one or that you want the blue one or that you want both?

The last two of these statements mean the same thing, so we would go for the first since it is simpler.

We can also omit one of the articles to create a statement such as

feli xa ne komus tê toblus
want.PRS NOM.I ne big.us or blue.us
I want a specific thing that is big or blue or both

or modify the statement by changing the specificity of the articles, as in

feli xa nā komus tē toblus

want.PRS NOM.I nā big.us or blue.us

I want something (not a specific thing) that is big or blue or big and blue

18. *sō* and *kō*

The *kōxō* word for 'yes' is *sō* and the *kōxō* word for 'no' is *kō*. This section was included for the sake of completeness since these words constitute a separate word class.